

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D3.9

ETHAI Model

March 2024

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab.	IT

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DoA	Description of Action
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
EB	Ethics Board
EC	European Commission
ES	Expert System
GA	General Assembly
H2020	Horizon 2020
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
Mx	Month x
No.	Number
PC	Project Coordinator
SotA	State of the art
TBD	To Be Decided
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

The ETHAI (“Ethics of AI”) model is conceived as a comprehensive framework to support an approach that truly incorporates ethics throughout the entire lifecycle of designing, developing, implementing and assessing artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare applications. Specifically conceived for the MES-CoBraD project, which addresses the challenge of assessing Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), the ETHAI model tackles critical questions concerning the ethical implications that arise with the introduction of an AI model into the healthcare landscape.

Addressing ethical issues in AI healthcare requires a holistic approach. As reliance on AI grows, it’s crucial not just to recognize, but to actively address these ethical considerations. Hence, ETHAI concentrates on three key aspects in this field.

Firstly, ETHAI prioritizes the ethical integrity of AI outputs. It requires continuous monitoring to prevent biases in data or algorithms that could lead to unfair patient outcomes.

Secondly, it discourages decisions based on non-universally accepted values or principles.

Thirdly, while the MES-CoBraD project doesn't support autonomous decision-making by expert systems, the ETHAI model aims to create a system that aligns as closely as possible with established ethical principles.

In this respect, the core ethical principles underpinning the ETHAI model are fundamental to guide the design and the assessment of AI systems. As yet taken into account in other deliverables, these principles include the principles of bioethics and the HLEG Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, which have represented the conceptual basis of the work made since now. In addition, care ethics has been incorporated. Although it’s more of an approach than a set of principles, its inherent values align well with this research. The specific principles are then categorized and assigned specific roles:

› **Bioethics:**

Respect for persons, emphasises and recognises the inherent dignity and autonomy of every patient (right to make informed decisions regarding care)

- *Beneficence*, designing and utilizing AI systems to benefit only patients (enhancing diagnoses, treatment recommendations, and overall healthcare outcomes)
- *Non-maleficence*, avoiding harm to patients and urging the mitigation of potential risks associated (*biases, malfunctions, etc.*)
- *Justice, fairness and equitable access to healthcare for all patients (against bias that could disadvantage certain populations)*

› **HLEG Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI:** these guidelines are harmonised with principles of bioethics for a more effective implementation of ethics

- *Human agency and oversight,*
- *Technical robustness and safety,*
- *Privacy and data governance,*
- *Transparency,*
- *Diversity,*
- *Non-discrimination and fairness,*
- *Environmental and societal wellbeing,*

- *Accountability.*

› **Care ethics:**

- *Voice, algorithm should maintain open the possibility of hearing different voices and not silence any voice.*
- *Relationships and interdependence, models do not take individuals as opponents in a contest of rights but as members of a network of relationships.*
- *Direct level, awareness that decisions should not result from an abstraction of the problem, eliminating the context.*
- *Vulnerability, algorithms should not prevent individuals from meeting their needs, especially the most basic ones*

Beyond principles, ETHAI model has integrated an ethics-by-design methodology for Artificial Intelligence systems, moving its steps from examples taken by other EU funded projects and by declining it to the very specific case of MES-CoBraD. The result of this operation is a model that not only detects and assesses risks but embeds ethics practices in the development of AI systems, having strong principles upon which give assessment criteria and evaluate use cases.

The ETHAI model, as described in the present deliverable, can be quickly summarized as follows:

1. Ethical Considerations Introduction:

- › Assess existing needs and potential ethical concerns, including stakeholders' perspectives.
- › Define and select foundational values and principles contextualized to the application domain of the Ethical AI (ETHAI) system.

2. Ethical Model Application:

- › Execute a comprehensive risk assessment to mitigate challenges inherent in AI system development.
- › Extract a set of requirements from preceding steps, encompassing context recognition, value/principle identification, ethical considerations, and risk assessment.
- › Embed ethical considerations, derived from identified risks, into the development process of the scrutinised AI system.
- › Translate ethical requirements into actionable assessment criteria.

3. Ethical Considerations Integration in Development Process (Ethics-by-Design):

- › Execute multiple iterations within a feedback loop to refine the development process.
- › Adapt risks, requirements, and assessment criteria iteratively based on the feedback loop and insights.
- › Conduct a final evaluation to gauge the ethical ramifications of the developed AI system.

The present deliverable describes this process and operationalises the work done on ethics during the project.

As a result of the work that is being done, the ETHAI model and its application in MES-CoBraD are incorporated in a working draft of the CEN/CENELEC that is currently under approval. This is also reported in the present deliverable.

1 INTRODUCTION

Earlier project deliverables specifically D2.3 and D2.5, established a framework for assessing ethical concerns and risks within the MES-CoBraD context. They also provide a set of ethical and legal standards to ensure that the research aligns with the stated ethical and legal framework. These standards guide the MES-CoBraD platform's development, ensuring its design and development adhere to the ethical and legal principles that shaped these criteria.

However, it must be pointed out that MES-CoBraD is not just a data management and analytics platform, but it will make use of advanced AI tools and techniques to boost its analytical power and act in all respects as a decision support system, capable of delivering diagnoses and suggesting healthcare treatments and plans.

As a result, the ethical evaluation of MES-CoBraD also encompasses issues related to artificial intelligence systems, particularly when applied to healthcare.

Ethics of AI as applied to healthcare is an extremely interesting field, being as it is at the intersection of two huge ethical reflection areas: that of AI in general, and that of medicine. In fact, with its attention to the human being, medical ethics represents a stimulating and engaging point of view under which to consider also general AI ethics. In this deliverable, we'll adopt an approach where medical ethics enriches AI ethics, focusing on aspects that profoundly define humans.

Once the MES-CoBraD Expert System (ES) platform is operational, the focus expands beyond design and development. Healthcare professionals will need to interact with the ES and its outputs. This includes tasks like evaluating the weight of an ES suggested diagnosis and deciding whether to inform patients about the ES's involvement.¹

The impact of AI on healthcare professional-patient interactions is just one piece of the puzzle. AI's introduction raises numerous ethical and practical questions. These include the transformation of healthcare delivery, the balance between transparency and trust, the distribution of research benefits and burdens, and the ethical use of patient data.

To optimize AI use in MES-CoBraD and healthcare overall, a deeper analysis and a more comprehensive model are needed. This model should serve two purposes: first, to guide the design and development of AI-powered healthcare systems, like MES-CoBraD and second, to provide a reference guide for healthcare professionals using these systems, helping them make informed decisions based on AI outputs.

In conclusion, three ethics issues are recognised to be of paramount importance:

- › How to ensure that the outputs of the system are ethically sound (for example that they are non-biased or are not based on hidden, not universally accepted values) and that hence do not bring to unethical results (for instance discrimination against a certain group).
- › How to use the outputs of the system (provided and accepted that they are valid) in a way that is ethically sound.
- › How to ensure that the system is able to take decisions that are ethically valid, in case it makes autonomous decisions.

Since the MES-CoBraD project's Expert System (ES) won't make autonomous decisions, the ETHAI model

¹ The fundamental relationship between healthcare professionals and patients is a critical determinant of successful healthcare delivery. The potential impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on this dynamic interaction is an emerging area of research. While some posit significant transformations to this relationship, with potential benefits or drawbacks, others maintain a more cautious stance, suggesting a potentially limited role for AI with minimal disruption to the established interaction.

for MES-CoBraD won't focus on the third point.

The ETHAI model aims thus to be the description of the entire process that leads to the development of an AI system that truly incorporates ethics principles and values, from the conception and design phase to the final assessment and deployment, being in this capable of – respectively - foresight ethical risks and potential issues and to mitigate them. As mentioned before, also the aspects pertaining to the use of the developed system should and will be considered, adding to the description of the process an outline of the decision making that ideally should be adopted when using the system (“ethical decision-making model”). This second aspect of the ETHAI model will be one of the contents to be analysed under deliverable D2.10.

Furthermore, it's important to note that the MES-CoBraD project goes beyond typical AI healthcare concerns like biases, accountability, and robustness. It also addresses unique challenges related to its focus on neurosciences, in particular on complex neurodegenerative diseases. With the spread of attempts of application of AI to neuro and cognitive sciences, an **entire new set of ethics issues connected with the use of AI emerged.**²

Thus, section 2 of this document explores ethical concerns surrounding AI in healthcare, both generally and specifically within the MES-CoBraD project (focusing on complex brain diseases). It also discusses relevant ethical principles and how MES-CoBraD has addressed them (further details in D2.5 and D2.9).

The core of this document (Section 3) introduces the ETHAI model, along with its guiding principles.

Section 4 and 5 delve into potential risks and assessment criteria specifically related to implementing the MES-CoBraD Expert System. Finally, Section 6 explores contributions to ethical standards, and section 7 concludes the document.

² Just to name the main and most important ones: the issue of the consequences of a pristine diagnosis of the probability of developing brain diseases like Alzheimer to healthy patients, that could have as an outcome a general worsening of the mental health conditions of patients, due to the loss of hope and to possible discriminations if the diagnosis is known; the risk of an overly medicalized/biologically reductionist approach to brain diseases, that overlooks psychological and socio/cultural factors and that does not allow to provide to patients the kind of combined and holistic therapy that could better benefit them; and finally the emerging issue of the privacy of neuroscience data, that must be tackled with a regulatory but also with an ethical approach, to prevent discriminatory or malevolent use of it (Coates McCall & Wexler, 2020; Kreitmair, 2019; Jwa & Poldrack, 2022; Aharoni et al., 2013).

2 THE DEBATE ON ETHICS OF AI APPLIED TO HEALTHCARE

2.1 OVERVIEW

A recent scoping review (Murphy et al., 2021) performed an analysis of papers dedicated to the application of AI to the healthcare³ field.

A recurring theme across most papers have as an object the problems of **data privacy and security, trustability of AI, accountability and responsibility, and of course the issue of the presence of biases** (either in the algorithms, the underlying assumptions or in the datasets). The authors highlight how none of those issues can be considered in isolation, but that they are interdependent and mutually reinforcing. Moreover, they call attention to some underrepresented themes, among which the absence of focus on low-medium income countries and on issues of social justice and the risk of jobs loss. Another concern raised by Karimian et al. is the lack of adequate consultation with end users. As a possible outcome of **discarding end users perspectives, with the risk that the ethics discourse is “confined to the hypothetical, devoid of the realities of everyday life”**. Another important point in common between the two reviews is the highlighting of a lack of reflection on how these recommendations could be optimally **secured through regulatory mechanisms and infrastructures**. One interesting aspect is that almost all the articles considered in Murphy et al are US or UK based, something that may have an influence on the ethical and philosophical stance of the analyses and assessments there contained.

(Karimian et al., 2022) conducted a scoping review from whence it emerged that the problems of **human autonomy, of data protection, of explicability and of fairness** (which can be assimilated to trustability) occupy most of the examined papers.

The authors explicitly based their scoping review on the **EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI**. They aimed to identify relevant principles, proposed solutions, and tools for ethical implementation of AI in healthcare. The review focused on extracting practical solutions from the analyzed papers and stakeholder opinions. Articles were searched in two databases: Medline (through PubMed) and Embase (through OVID). The studies were conducted in various healthcare settings, including primary care, mental health, intensive care units, and community hospital. The studies involved healthcare professionals, caregivers, some patient groups, and health informatic leaders. Quite interestingly, **the scoping review shows that there is a recurrent gap in the gathering of stakeholders needs**: a few articles considered a limited number of healthcare providers and patients but other groups of stakeholders in healthcare such as regulatory authorities, healthcare facility managers, AI developers and vulnerable groups of people have not been taken into account, something that opens up interesting routes both at the policy and at the ethical assessment level.

Figure 1 - Map of outcomes (i.e., ethical principles) measured by the number of studies in the scoping review from Karimian, G., Petelos, E. & Evers

Also (Zhang & Zhang, 2023) discuss the factors that have more impact in trustworthy medical AI. They identify **data quality, algorithmic bias, transparency, responsibility allocation and the menaces posed to patients’ and clinicians’ autonomy** as the main issues emerging from the literature.

³ For a comprehensive review of AI applied to healthcare, not focused primarily on ethical issues, see (Alowais et al., 2023) and (Kumar et al., 2023)

Figure 2 - Factors affecting trustworthy medical AI from (Zhang & Zhang 2023)

They focus on **the need to develop more specific and operational guidelines and recommendations**, something that should be done under the guidance of ethical principles, operational guidelines that should then be translated into governmental regulations or departmental rules so that ethical principles can have legal and administrative effects.

Particularly noteworthy is Corrêa et al.’s (2023) meta-analysis, which dwarfs prior reviews by examining a massive dataset of 200 papers. The figure they provide (Figure 3, based on Corrêa et al., 2023) summarizes the most frequently considered ethical principles: **transparency, trustworthiness, justice, privacy, and accountability**. These principles align closely with those identified in other reviews explored in this document:

Figure 3 - Outline of the ethical principles present in the scientific literature from (Corrêa et al., 2023)

According to their analysis , one of the points that the authors underline is **the existing gap between established principles and their actual application** (a concern that is shared also by (Fjeld et al., 2020)). In other words, **most articles contain normative statements but do not indicate the means to achieve them**.

The principle of **transparency/explainability** in particular is of great relevance also because, as (Russo et al., 2023) points out, it is a **connection point between ethics and epistemology** of AI, especially in healthcare: **we trust the results because we trust the process, we trust the process because it is transparent**.

J. Morley and L. Floridi (Morley et al., 2020) explore the comparison of ethical principles in AI across various guidelines, documents, and papers. They observe that these principles ultimately stem from

beneficence (AI benefits people and the environment), non-maleficence (AI is robust and secure), respect for autonomy (AI aligns with human values), fairness (AI is just), and accountability and understandability (AI is explicable), therefore adopting an approach that merges the principle-based approach to bioethics with AI ethics. Notably, the authors delve into the need for a more practical, hands-on approach to AI ethics principles. They propose breaking down each principle into seven facets, **corresponding to different stages of algorithmic development**, including business and use-case development, design phase, training and test data procurement, building, testing, deployment, and monitoring.

2.2 MES-COBAD BASELINE OF ETHICS PRINCIPLES AND VALUES

To establish the MES-CoBraD approach for assessing AI compliance with ethical principles and values, the following subsection provides an overview of existing theories, identifying the one most suitable for the project context.

2.2.1 EXISTING ETHICAL THEORIES

Ethical theories and approaches can be divided in **three general frameworks: consequentialism, non-consequentialism, and agent-centered theories**.

Consequentialism is the ethical framework that focuses on the future effects of the action, considering the people who will be affected. In the decision-making process, the question is about what outcomes are desirable in a certain situation and which actions will lead to those outcomes.

The following approaches can be listed under consequentialism:

- › Utilitarian approach: classical utilitarianism is a consequentialist ethical theory designed in the 19th Century by the philosopher Jeremy Bentham (1748–1832) and refined by his follower, John Stuart Mill (1806–1873). The utilitarian approach to ethics affirms that an action should produce the greatest balance of good over harm for as many people as possible. So, in utilitarianism, the most ethical choice is the one that will produce the greatest amount of good for the greatest number of people.
- › Common good approach: this approach has its roots in Jean Jacques Rousseau’s (1712-1778) philosophical theory of the “general will”, the will of the people. According to the common good approach, individuals’ own good is linked to the good of the community. Community members have common values and goals, so every moral action should contribute to the community life. To make ethical choices, it’s necessary to recognize the goals that are shared in society.

Non-Consequentialism is the ethical framework that focuses on the intentions of the people making ethical decisions, not on the consequence of their actions.

The following approaches can be listed under non-consequentialism:

- › Duty approach: also called “deontological ethics”, it has its greatest exponent in the philosopher Emmanuel Kant (1724-1804). According to the duty approach to decision making, what makes an action “ethical” is the performer of the action’s intentions, regardless of the good or bad consequences that may be produced. Doing the right thing means doing one’s duty so the agent must always act correctly, according to his\her duty, even if the outcome of the action doesn’t bring any good or benefit.
- › Rights approach: according to this approach, the ethical action must be based on the respect of the human dignity and the unalienable rights of those who are affected by the action. The rights which need to be respected can be intended as natural (considered as derived from nature, right reason, or religion) or conventional (created by society).

- › Justice approach: also called the “fairness” approach, this approach states that the fair action is the one that treats everyone the same, without any or discrimination. According to the most influent exponent of this theory, the American philosopher John Rawls (1921- 2002), fair ethical principles are those that would be chosen in a hypothetical contract by free people in a situation of equality. This would guarantee equal treatment, therefore, justice.

Agent-centered theories don't take into consideration the morality of the action but the ethical status of the agent.

The following approaches can be classified under the agent-centered theories:

- › Virtue approach: virtue ethics is one of the oldest ethical frameworks, it has its origins in Plato and Aristotle's ancient Greece. In this approach, good actions are the consequence of certain ideal virtues. Virtues are excellent traits of character that come from individual dispositions, like honesty, courage, compassion, generosity, tolerance, fairness, prudence. Bad actions, on the other hand, come from vices such as cowardice and ignorance.
- › Care ethics: it is a feminist contemporary philosophical perspective that tries to overcome the three previously seen frameworks. What is crucial in ethics of care is to respond to individuals and their specific needs assuming that human condition is relational. Care ethics is concerned with the flourishing of individuals in the framework of their relationships and interdependence. To act ethically, compassion, empathy and kindness are fundamental tools to hear and respect the feelings of each person involved.

Given these different approaches, the decision-making process should start from asking the following questions:

- › Which option will produce the best outcome and do the least harm for as many people as possible? (The Utilitarian Approach)
- › Which action is good for the whole community, not for just some members? (The Common Good Approach)
- › Which action ensures that I fulfil my duty? (The Duty approach)
- › Which action respects the rights of all who are involved? (The Rights Approach)
- › Which action treats people equally? (The Justice Approach)
- › What person should I be in order to always act ethically? (The Virtue Approach)
- › Which option appropriately takes into account the concerns, relationships, and feelings of the person involved? (The Care Ethics Approach).

2.2.2 MES-CoBRAD APPROACH

From the analysis in **Error! Reference source not found.**, it is clear that **most of the SotA approaches, including the EU Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, are based on on a version of the consequentialism approach (“principlism”), that consists on basing the judgment regarding the ethicality of a certain action on the adherence to a certain set of principles.**

The principle-based approach , widely used, faces critiques. A key concern for this project is that **principles alone don't equate to values.** Critics argue principlism **lacks a strong ethical foundation** and needs a **core value system** as a **reference point.** However, **principlism's flexibility** is a strength. It can **adapt** and

integrate with various value systems. Therefore, exploring its integration with a defined value system remains a valuable avenue.

MES-CoBraD will reconcile a principle-based consequentialist approach with an agent-centered theory (specifically the Ethics of Care), that should work as an ethical reference to the principles and make ethical decisions possible.

Therefore, MES-CoBraD adopts **a combination of the EU Ethics Guidelines for trustworthy AI requirements** (i.e., Human agency and oversight; Technical robustness and safety; Privacy and data governance; Transparency; Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness; Environmental and societal well-being; Accountability) **together with the so-called “four principles of bioethics”** (Autonomy/Respect, Beneficence, Non Maleficence and Justice) of Beauchamp and Childress (Beauchamp & Childress, 2001), but provides ethical foundation to them with the Ethics of Care provides approach.

As above-stated, also the Beauchamp and Childress approach to principlism is not free of criticism. For instance (Shea, 2020) argues that those principles lack a proper value theory (namely a theory that what is good and bad, and why) at their basis and for this reason they are not a sufficient foundation for bioethics. The author argues that **without a theory of what is good and bad (and he adopts the perspective of the so-called prudential values, namely “well-being”) the four principles are not capable of offering true orientation in ethical choices**, because the “right” line of action depends strongly on the foundational values, i.e. on what “good” and so for example “beneficence” are considered to be. He makes the example of an ancient cognitively impaired who has suffered a stroke and is now recovered in hospital, surviving only thanks to life sustaining treatments. To determine and compare the benefits and burdens of the different treatment options it is essential to identify what counts as a benefit or as a burden.

Giving their enduring role as the foundation for most bioethical research and literature, and their wide adoption in healthcare settings, the Beauchamp and Childress principles remain highly relevant. Therefore, they will be employed in this project as valuable “ethical tools” to guide its work.

On the other hand, further different principles have been identified. For instance, it has been argued (Dubler & Liebman, 2011) that one of the guiding principles should be that of reaching a mediation between doctor and patient point of views, in a sort of narrative setting, while (Varkey, 2020) in his Principles of Clinical Ethics and Their Application to Practice makes an attempt at formulating an entirely different model, with caring as the central value.

To conciliate those criticisms and the willingness of introducing further relevant principles within the MES-CoBraD approach, the AI requirements and the biomedical principles have been combined with the ethical values adopted by the Ethics of Care approach. Its combination with a purely principlist approach however complex, as they move from quite different point of views, has been applied in the project context as described in the following sections.

The next subsections illustrate the four principles of bioethics and the Ethics of Care approach.

2.2.3 THE FOUR PRINCIPLES OF BIOETHICS

The first and foremost principle of bioethics is **autonomy**, that in the medical ethics context means **the moral right of the patient to self-determination**, a principle that – especially in contemporary western contexts and from the XXI century on – becomes almost absolute, **making the subject the ultimate agent of the decision-making process**, even when there may be cases where the patient experiences severe difficulties in taking a reasonable and reasoned decision regarding his/her health. Of course, this principle implies that the patient is capable of fully understanding what is being proposed to him/her,

and consequently that has (that he/she has been given) all the information that he/she needs to reach this understanding as well as the necessary training/explanations. Autonomy, as it is interpreted in the context of the present deliverable, **concerns not only the patient but also the clinician, whose judgment should not be hindered by the interference of external factors** (e.g., diagnoses provided by an algorithm) or by the lack of transparency. For this reason, also when a human is appointed to supervise the working of an algorithm, it must be ensured that he/she has all the necessary knowledge, information and understanding to judge correctly and that he/she is not unduly influenced.

As per the **beneficence** principle, in ethical theories it has a really broad meaning, referring to every action, norm, disposition, having the goal of benefitting the others. Beneficence had a great fortune in ethical theories. For example, it is at the centre of Mill's utilitarianism, where **an action or practice is deemed morally right in comparison to any alternative if it maximizes the overall positive consequences (such as happiness, according to Mill) or minimizes the overall negative consequences (such as unhappiness, according to Mill)**. To be noted that the weighting of the consequences must be done taking into account all possible affected parties, so it is necessary to consider positive benefits and negative effects over all persons affected, not on just one individual. Rules of beneficence require that they are actively followed (do good), are in other words **positive obligations**, that for this reason are more demanding and more subject to interpretation than non-maleficence rules (help others as contrasted with do not harm others). To be noted that beneficence, with its imperative to benefit others, may be in contrast with autonomy, shifting into paternalism. The two principles are in fact in close connection. Also, the principle of beneficence requires that for an agent to be moral he/she acts in the best interest of the others (of the patient in case of medicine), even in contrast with his/her interests. In Biomedical ethics the adoption of the principle of beneficence is traceable to publication of the Belmont Report in 1978, that established that beneficence was one of the three basic principles of research ethics, alongside with respect for persons (under which it is possible to subsume autonomy) and justice. It's interesting how beneficence is also in strict relationship with justice, when considered under the lens of social justice and so of the equal distribution of burdens and benefits into society.

Non maleficence (do not harm) is the principle that has an easier translation - together with autonomy - in artificial intelligence ethics, thanks to its strict correlation with risks analysis. It's important to underline that non-maleficence is different from non-malevolence, that concerns the (non) malevolent intention. **Non-maleficence is about the results of an action, that must be such as to maximise the benefits with respect to the potential burdens.** To satisfy the principle of non-maleficence a **risk/benefit analysis** must be performed to decide whether a certain treatment (in healthcare ethics) or a certain course of action should be undertaken, or if a certain product should be developed or released into the market.

Finally, **justice** is intended mainly as **fairness and equity**: it states that **the benefits (and the burdens) must be equitably distributed, and that any decision is taken on the basis of a recognized set of standards and reasons that fully justify that course of action and that decision, that should never be based on discriminatory or unjust reasons** (e.g. deciding what healthcare treatment to administer in reason of age, gender, or ethnicity). To satisfy this principle, not only there shouldn't be any open discrimination or unfair treatment, but **also unwanted biases** that could compromise the fairness of a certain decision or result should be actively avoided. The principle of Justice gains particular relevance in healthcare AI assessments because bias is a major issue that can compromise the validity and fairness of these systems.

It is important to stress out that the **principles should not be seen as absolute rules**. Since from their first formulation it was pointed out that **they have to be adapted to the context** and that **negotiations between principles had to be made**: crucially Beauchamp and Childress's principles are not intended as absolutes. Instead, they serve as a framework for ongoing dialogue. This balanced approach is essential, as the principles need to be weighed against each other in specific contexts and by the individuals applying them.

2.2.4 THE VALUES AT THE BASIS OF THE ETHICS OF CARE

To adopt a more comprehensive approach, the project reconsidered the sufficiency of the sole four principles as a basis for our model, leading to a change of approach also with respect to the first project's deliverables. This is even more valid considering that the aim here is developing a model for the assessment of the MES-CoBraD's artificial intelligence component that can effectively address all the ethical issues that emerge or that (on the basis of a literature review) could emerge as a consequence of its adoption inside healthcare contexts.

In this sense, during the course of the project's research, **it became evident that the context of application is not neutral** and that, maintaining the basic ethical values, also the particularities of the different context of application, like in this case the healthcare, and the healthcare applied to complex neurodegenerative diseases, must be considered, as well as the specificities of an approach to ethics that is focused on the individual not as a monad, but as part of a complex network of social and human relationships.

Thus, an **Ethics of Care** approach has been added, based on the reflection that **the moral agent ought not to be principally construed in relation to independence, equality of power and influence**. Instead, **the perspective here adopted emphasizes the interrelatedness, vulnerability, and dependency among agents**, frequently manifesting in asymmetric dynamics (Pettersen, 2011). In Gilligan's words, the world that care ethics describes is a "world that coheres through human connection rather than through systems of rules"(Gilligan, 1982).

On this line, the project will adopt an **alternative model strongly based on an ethics of care approach to bioethics**. Ethics of care seems indeed to be particularly apt to act as a basis for an AI assessment model applied to healthcare as it shares some traits with what lies at the core of healthcare, namely an attention to everything is human and to what it means to take care of other human beings. As stated by (Varkey, 2020) "besides the technical expertise of a physician, the human element of caring (one human to another) is needed".

Care ethics is born in psychology (Gilligan 1982), not in philosophy, and from the very beginning it has an ambivalent stance, meaning both the description of a social practice (the caring) and a foundational moral value (care). (Chadha-Sridhar, 2023) tries to reconcile these point of views describing care as a "thick" concept, i.e. a concept that combines evaluation (values) and non-evaluative description. In other words, **care is an attitude, a behaviour, but also a normative moral value that can lay at the foundation of a moral theory of good and evil**. In this sense, as the four principles of bioethics are value agnostic, care ethics and principles of bioethics can indeed be reconciled, as the first can act as the value theory of the other. Besides, as (Collins, 2015) underlines, when taking ethical decisions we can divide the process in two: deliberation (namely the procedures we use when making ethical decisions) and justification (the reasons for a certain action). Principles can comfortably have a role in the deliberation process but not be the only foundation for justification; similarly, it is certainly possible to formulate care ethics principles that act as a general reference for justification, but those principles will be different from the classical four principles of bioethics (for instance, Eva Feder Kittay's 'principle of social responsibility for care': '[t]o each according to his or her need for care, from each according to his or her capacity for care, and such support from social institutions as to make available resources and opportunities to those providing care, so that all will be adequately attended in relations that are sustaining') (Kittay, 2011).

One aspect to which it is necessary to pay attention is that care ethics is not monolithic and completely developed, but it's a theory still in evolution, with multiple articulations and different approaches. In this work there will be considered two ethics of care inspired approaches in particular: one will be "Ethics of Care as moral Grounding for AI" by Carolina Villegas Galaviz, a paper that emphasizes **the effects that the vast adoption of algorithmic decision could have on human beings** (borrowing a term from the artist Mimi Onuoha the author speaks of "algorithmic violence" meaning the fact that sometimes the use of an algorithm may prevent people from meeting their basic needs) on **four aspects in particular: voice** ("which voices are being silenced with the development of this algorithm?"), **relationships and interdependence**

(“which interdependence relationships can be affected or ignored by the development of this algorithm? Would emotions be an eliminated essential part of the kind of decision that is being automated?”), **attention to context** (“does this algorithm imply the elimination of context and circumstances when they can be an essential part of a future decision?”) and finally **vulnerability** (“does this algorithm prevent the possibility of fostering the needs of protected classes, people at risk of social exclusion, or marginalized stakeholders?”). (Villegas-Galaviz & Martin, 2023) uses the concept of “moral distance” to better exemplify the difference between a principlist and a care ethics approach. In particular (as outlined also by (Huber & Munro, 2014) and by (Mittelstadt, 2019)) she argues that principles may lead to an excessive abstraction, generating a kind of bureaucratic distance. Ethics of care approach is there defined as “a shared understanding that **ethical decision-making should consider interdependent relationships, context and circumstances**, attend to particular vulnerabilities, and also should **respond to different points of view, and hear different voices**”. In other words, a Care Ethics approach does not consist in replacing a set of principles with another set, but rather in entirely shifting the point of view, fully taking into account the complexities of the moral reasoning and adopting as a guiding light an attitude towards helping the others, in particular the most fragile.

In conclusion, the **ethics of care should not be seen as a complete in itself alternative to principlism but rather as a complement, that steps in where an individual approach to a specific person (while staying in a specific framework) is needed**. For this reason, in the next section, where a risk assessment analysis for MES-CoBraD’s Expert System is conducted, **ethics of care will be considered as a fifth principle alongside with the classical four principles of bioethics**, but it will shed light also on the risks identified relatively to the autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence and justice principles.

3 THE MES-COBRAD ETHAI MODEL

In the previous sections the discussion about the intersection of the ethics of AI, the bioethics and the Ethics of Care was outlined, and the project's position in this regard was described.

Following the route traced by D2.3 and D2.5, the **principles of bioethics** with the **EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI**, operationalised in the **ALTAI** questionnaire for self-evaluation⁴, has been combined. Additionally, due to the specific domain of the project in the neuro and cognitive sciences, the **Ethics of Care** approach is taken into consideration providing a perspective that complements traditional bioethical principles and EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. **The effort to harmonise these diverse ethical frameworks reflects a commitment to fostering a responsible and human-centred approach to artificial intelligence development and implementation.**

In the present section the working of the project framework based on the ETHAI model and how is tailored to the project context will be described. **First, some of the already existing assessment tools will be described and discussed**, to inscribe the project model into the current theoretical framework. **Then the ETHAI model will be outlined**, also showing how it distinguishes from the examined assessment tools and frameworks.

EU projects SHERPA⁵ (*Project Sherpa – Shaping the Ethical Dimensions of Smart Information Systems a European Perspective*, s.d.) and SIENNA⁶ (*Project Sienna*), along with their respective methodologies rooted in **ethics-by-design**, will be taken as prominent examples of the current standards for assessing ethics in artificial intelligence.

It has to be noted that in this chapter the all process underlying the application of the ETHAI model will be outlined, although only a part of it is applied to the MES-CoBraD case.

3.1 OVERVIEW OF ASSESSMENT TOOLS

The ETHAI model is intended to be an assessment tool for AI, with a strong basis in ethical principles, while retaining a flexibility that adheres to the particular field of investigation in which it is applied.

In this, ETHAI follows the tradition of other European projects integrating ethics in the research and development of technologies, namely the AI and its application in various fields. In this section, an overview of the relevant assessment tools is given through a literature review and a discussion of the main pros and cons that can be seen from their comparison.

Given the escalating interest not only in the ethical dimensions of artificial intelligence but also in its regulation, it is increasingly apparent that AI Impact Assessments will wield significant influence in shaping future AI governance frameworks. While there is considerable discourse surrounding various forms of impact assessments, there is a pressing need to explore how they can be seamlessly integrated into existing organizational frameworks, such as risk management processes.

As AI tools and models should provide benefits upon individuals, organisations, and society at large, the role of the assessments is to check and verify if this promise is maintained, as well as to mitigate potential threats or negative consequences when applied to particular domains of research and application.

There are some shortcomings that characterize the landscape of AI evaluation in our time. The point to make clear is that quite often **these evaluations excessively stress technical aspects** (for instance the robustness and the resilience of the system, or its vulnerability to cyberattacks) **over the broader societal implications and ethical considerations** inherent in AI systems, that they fail to capture. It should never be forgotten that evaluations also serve the crucial function of assessing the acceptability of AI systems,

⁴ The Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence - <https://altai.insight-centre.org/>

⁵ <https://www.project-sherpa.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.sienna-project.eu/>

ensuring they align with societal values and ethical norms. The overarching goal is to foster the development and deployment of reliable and trustworthy AI technologies.

The absence of universally accepted models to assess AI applications is evident. Currently, a multitude of ethical assessments exist, leading to confusion about which one to employ.. These shortcomings underline the urgent need for a more holistic approach to evaluation. On the legislative front, even though the AI Act has been approved, the question remains also considering the *vacatio legis* of two years before full enforcement and the fact that it has validity only in the EU. Many other normative attempts are being carried on in other countries, in some cases based on quite different approaches. In this sense **widely recognized and adaptable ethical assessment models could serve as a valid and flexible complement to normative framework** and thus would be even more important.

Similarly, the EU has positioned itself at the forefront of the question, by pioneering the development of assessment tools like **ALTAI** (*Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self-assessment*, 2020), which directly stems from the EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. The purpose of the ALTAI self-assessment is to operationalise and implement the seven key requirements for trustworthiness (Human Agency and Oversight; Technical Robustness and Safety; Privacy and Data Governance; Transparency; Diversity Non-discrimination and Fairness; Societal and Environmental Well-being; Accountability) into an accessible checklist divided into steps to follow. Utilising this tool helps mitigate potential risks associated with AI deployment and establish a framework for responsible development and deployment practices. While the ALTAI questionnaire is grounded in established ethical principles (Respect for human autonomy, Prevention of harm, Fairness, Explicability), it maintains a degree of **adaptability**. This is because the questions, framed with a broader scope, can be applied to various research areas without compromising their core purpose. This flexibility allows developers and deployers of diverse AI systems to leverage the tool effectively in their self-assessment process.

ALTAI, as a framework, faces several challenges and opportunities for improvement in its application across various organisations and stages of development (Radclyffe et al., 2023) (Stahl & Leach, 2023).

Firstly, an issue of ALTAI is that it should work for organizations at all different stages of development, in the sense that it should be tailored for their governance level, small projects or SMEs, big companies or projects developed worldwide or agencies, but in fact it works effectively only for certain kinds of organizations at a certain step of the development of their AI projects. This raises questions about the adaptability of ALTAI and its relevance to organisations in different phases of maturity. In addition, just like other important factors, ethics can't just be added on a system in the final assessment stage but needs to enter in all phases of development. ALTAI instead resembles more to a checklist for a finalised product rather than to a flexible framework that grows alongside the developed technology since from the initial conception and design phases. The advice provided after completing the questionnaire appear to be tailored more towards market introduction specifics rather than offering tips or advice for early-stage technology aimed at achieving an effective ethics by design. Moreover, domain-specific adjustments should be made, incorporating and accounting for questions that align with the unique context of development.

ALTAI goes a step further by using a visually appealing radar chart to showcase its assessment results. This chart effectively highlights the strengths and weaknesses (faults and critical areas) of AI projects. This could represent a criticality, especially for projects or organisations in early stages of work. Obtaining a low score could generate a desire to conceal critical points, in an attempt to show that everything is on track, thus deterring transparency and impeding efforts to build trust. This without offering any support by which effectively co-design ethics in an AI tool or model. This shows how important it is to match governance with how experienced an organization is with AI.

Eventually, ALTAI doesn't consider the relative risk of AI systems when assessing them, the risk assessment is a separate phase. It would be better instead if risk assessment was conducted during the evaluation process instead of doing it separately. This way, governance can match the risks of an

organization's AI use, encouraging ALTAI application without worrying about getting low scores.

ALTAI is also considered as part of the *resolve phase* inside Z-Inspection® (Zicari et al., 2021) process for assessing trustworthy AI, in which scores are defined, possible tensions are addressed or resolved, recommendations are given, while highlighting new trade-offs a setting up an ethical maintenance to monitor the future development of the AI system. Z-Inspection® is a process for the auditing of an AI system, but also useful in the inception phase for helping to raise awareness on critical ethical, social, legal, and technical issues. Z-Inspection® leverages established frameworks and checklists for the verification of the system, while tailoring the assessment methodology for specific domains and contexts. The aim is to replace self-assessments, as they are considered not sufficient for the scope while also posing the risk of internal conflict of interests inside the organisation, and to include experts for verifying given indicators for trustworthiness. Wanting to find similarities with our work, Z-Inspection® takes as use case a study in healthcare, where ethical issues were identified starting from the role of clinicians and their possible problems with the use of AI, to the choice of requirements in the EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and the setting of a questionnaire. Another key aspect which is agreeable, is that effective checklists in evidence-based medical software should be designed with both user roles and existing workflows in mind. This ensures that clinicians feel supported by the software, following clear procedures while avoiding a paternalistic approach.

A different kind of approach is represented by projects like **SHERPA**, that try to operationalise ethics guidelines in work instructions to incorporate ethics into the design process of the technology. This is reflected in several approaches of these type of projects, in particular in the “Guidelines for the Ethical Development of AI and Big Data Systems: An Ethics by Design approach”⁷, where the classification of guidelines ranges from high-level principles to specific actions, with intermediate steps offering more detailed conditions.

While high-level guidelines embody abstract values, operational ones are closely linked to specific practices or actions to be taken. Thus, the report moves from abstract principles to practical instructions for AI and big data development. Also, here the high-level guidelines come from the EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, while the intermediate steps are sub-principles derived from the conceptual refinement and problematisation of those, intertwined with processes inside the technology development.

⁷ <https://www.project-sherpa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/development-final.pdf>

SHERPA High-level requirements and sub-requirements
<p>1 Human agency, liberty and dignity: Positive liberty, negative liberty and human dignity</p>
<p>2 Technical robustness and safety: Including resilience to attack and security, fall back plan and general safety, accuracy, reliability and reproducibility</p>
<p>3 Privacy and data governance: Including respect for privacy, quality and integrity of data, access to data, data rights and ownership</p>
<p>4 Transparency: Including traceability, explainability and communication</p>
<p>5 Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness: Avoidance and reduction of bias, ensuring fairness and avoidance of discrimination, and inclusive stakeholder engagement</p>
<p>6 Individual, societal and environmental wellbeing: Sustainable and environmentally friendly AI and big data systems, individual wellbeing, social relationships and social cohesion, and democracy and strong institutions</p>
<p>7 Accountability: auditability, minimisation and reporting of negative impact, internal and external governance frameworks, redress, and human oversight</p>

Figure 4 - SHERPA high level requirements

1 Human Agency

Requirement 10: Potential for impact on autonomy.

In the business understanding and evaluation phases, assess and ensure that:

- evaluation of the end-users’ awareness about how the system may impact their autonomy is performed to determine if it is appropriate to make people aware of this impact, and if so, then ensure their awareness (e.g., if an end-user is using the system in a medical capacity, you need to ensure that the functionality of the system and the context in which it is used does not undermine their informed consent to any treatment options);
- the system does not harm individuals’ autonomy (i.e., the freedom and ability to make one’s own goals and influence the outcomes of those decisions);
- any interference the system has with the stakeholders’ decision-making process (e.g., by recommending actions, decisions, or by how it presents stakeholders with options) is justified and minimised.

2 Negative Liberty

Requirement 11: Fundamental rights

In all phases, assess and ensure that:

- the system does not interfere with fundamental liberties of users or other stakeholders (including, e.g., freedom of movement, freedom of assembly, and freedom of speech).

Figure 5 - Example of SHERPA sub requirements

Indeed, metaphorically, the translation of ethical requirements into the language of technology involves a process like coding, where each requirement is articulated into sub strings meticulously detailed that instantiate rules to be adhered to. This transformation provides the technology with a normative framework, effectively embedding the high-level principles into its structure.

This “coding” of ethical requirements encompasses the essence of **ethical design** within the technological realm. **By encoding ethical norms, e.g. responsibility and accountability, into the technology, is ensured that ethical considerations are not merely an afterthought, but an integral part of its design and functionality.** Applying this model requires a deep understanding of both the ethical imperatives at play and the technical intricacies of the technology itself. **Ethicists and developers must navigate together this**

intersection, ensuring that the translated rules not only reflect the ethical principles, but also align seamlessly with the intended scope of the developed technology.

Similarly, SIENNA project provides a five-level-model (cfr. D5.7 SHERPA and D5.4 SIENNA):

- › **Ethics by Design** values (EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI) that guide the AI system development. Violating these values, the entire system should be considered unethical
- › **Ethics requisites**, values that AI systems should reinforce
- › **Ethics guidelines**, steps by which AI systems are created, ensuring that each step (or task) is ethical
- › **AI methodologies** (Agile, CRISP-DM, V-model). Each methodology offers its own steps and sequence.
- › **AI tools and methods** specific programmatic artefacts and processes deployed within the development process (e.g., Datasheets for Datasets) to undertake Ethics by Design

This approach is clearer in the light of the fact that **SIENNA** has covered diverse fields of study during its lifetime as well as the possibility of assessing them. Fields accounted for are: *genomics*, *human enhancement*, and *AI and robotics*, thus leading to the construction of a model that would be relevant for each one of them. Particularly, the focus was set to socio-economic factors and more broadly to the impact on human rights.

The effort in developing the approach of SIENNA and SHERPA projects is synthesised in the article *Ethics by design for artificial intelligence* (Brey & Dainow, 2023), where the Ethics by Design for AI approach (EbD-AI) is described and which reflects the same approach that has also recently been integrated into the European Commission's ethics assessment process for AI projects⁸. The article takes its starting point from the *European Parliament resolution of 12 February 2019 on a comprehensive European industrial policy on artificial intelligence and robotics* (Texts Adopted - A Comprehensive European Industrial Policy on Artificial Intelligence and Robotics - Tuesday, 12 February 2019, s.d.), where the role of ethics by design is formally recognised and endorsed.

The main stance of ethics by design approach is that **technology is inherently not neutral, and it's recognised that values can be integrated into the design process to some extent**. Central to this notion is the understanding that design choices are also not exempted by moral agency, as they can wield significant ethical implications. Computer science has indeed to do with the incorporation of values into design, as evidenced by established principles such as Privacy by Design, Secure by Design, Transparency by Design, Safety by Design and Design for Sustainability, which also demonstrate that a wide range of values can be incorporated into the design process, often with the aim of actualising or sustaining these values.

Instead of engaging in philosophical discussions, Ethics by Design for AI approach (EbD-AI) relies on the belief that predefined tasks are more comprehensible to engineers, thus proposing a framework divided in tasks as a solution that can be integrated, giving ethics the role of a “variable” to be added in all the levels of the system development processes.

In practice, this translates into the conversion of moral values and principles into requirements for the AI system in question, leading to the other steps of the framework:

- › **Assessment** to control if any core moral values are violated. If yes, the AI, as envisioned, is already *unethical*.
- › **Instantiation** of moral values as characteristics the AI system should possess, providing ethical design

⁸ European Commission, “Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence (1.0),” European Commission - DG Research and Innovation, 22 2021. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-by-design-and-ethics-of-use-approaches-for-artificial-intelligence_he_en.pdf

requirements.

- › **Mapping** high-level ethical design requirements into specific procedures and actions to be taken during the design process.
- › **Application** of a generic model of development into which values have already been translated into AI-specific requirements, mapping it into a chosen methodology (e.g. AGILE, Crisp-DM)
- › **Implementation** of Ethics by Design protocols during the development process in accord with the mapping done in the previous step.

Then, after choosing the principles of reference, a generic model is divided into six phases as outlined in the image below:

Figure 6 - The six phases of Ethics by Design for AI approach (EbD-AI)

At the end of the model, during the testing and evaluation phase, an ethical assessment must test if the system is meeting the given ethical requirements. If the EbD-AI approach has been implemented accordingly, most issues will result to be yet addressed. Moreover, it is important to involve all the stakeholders affected by the testing, assessing the real-world use of the system and verify even with a checklist the overall ethical compliance. It must be noted that during the testing not everything can be changed in the system, as most characteristics are already codified in previous steps.

However, **the Ethics-by-Design model for AI is not exempted by criticism:**

- › preselects the values, thus is not flexible in the choice.
- › too focused on the application of ethical principles.
- › the approach is too complicated for designers.

Although the criticisms of the models considered can be shared, it is equally true that they represent a point from which to start and take example, trying to fill the conceptual knots that remain unresolved and that have been highlighted. **The ETHAI model in MES-CoBraD aims to do just that, proposing a new approach to the ethics of artificial intelligence and specifically for the medical field.**

3.2 THE ETHAI MODEL – THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Having described the most common used assessment tools and identified their weaknesses, this paragraph aims at describing the ETHAI model in its general form and its conceptual framework by starting precisely from the highlighted criticisms. The factors that the ETHAI model considers and from which it moves are:

- › Which **type of organisation** or **project** wants to implement the AI system?
- › In which **context of application or domain** is developed the system?
- › What **principles** should be considered aside the normative and legal framework?
- › How to translate principles and values into **specific actions**?

- › How to operationalise these **practices**?
- › Why it is not sufficient to embed only principles in the system and instead also provide a care ethics approach for the dimension of the human relationships?

Answering these questions makes it possible to outline the actions that will be followed to arrive at the production of an artificial intelligence model that can support the designers and the developers in the production of an AI system that can be considered ethical, starting from its conceptualisation. An ethical evaluation model should offer a customisable framework that can be adapted based on the size, scope, and governance structure of the organisation or project considered. This ensures that smaller projects or startups, as well as larger corporations or government agencies, can utilise the model effectively by catering their needs based on the resources and expertise they have. In this regard, the model should be also flexible in its implementation, allowing projects and organisations to integrate ethical considerations into their existing workflows and decision-making frameworks. This will also include specific recommendations for establishing ethical oversight mechanisms, accountability structures, and compliance procedures.

ALTAI's broad scope, while offering a comprehensive assessment, can be a limitation. This lack of focus may make it challenging to adapt the tool to specific contexts like healthcare applications.

This calls for an approach that not only addresses the immediate needs of product evaluation, but also fosters ethical design principles throughout the developmental stages, ensuring that ethical considerations are integrated seamlessly into the structure of artificial intelligence technologies. This is what the ETHAI model, developed in the context of the MES-CoBraD project, aims to do. Early in the process, questions about potential biases, privacy concerns, environmental impact, and societal implications are introduced, leading to the definition and choice of the principles to be followed and that serve as the foundational framework for the ethical model. Then, guiding principles are complemented with ethical standards, e.g. bioethics for clinical studies with human patients⁹, providing a comprehensive structure that informs decision-making, guides actions, and ensures accountability. Within this framework, universally recognised principles such as fairness, transparency, accountability, are of utmost importance, thus having the possibility to guide stakeholders – when making design decision about the system - in navigating complex ethical issues and helping them to take ethically founded design decisions.

When applying the model, at this stage, namely **after having discerned the context and having accordingly determined principles and values, a risk assessment must be conducted** to address the challenges posed by the development of the AI system and to verify its adherence to the chosen principles. Risks may include technical failures, security vulnerabilities, privacy violations, and address the consequences of possible social discrimination for those affected or loss of employment for workers. This allows the entire organisation or project that is developing the system to have a clear view of the possible risks that have been highlighted and circumscribed by the application of the principles on technology development.

Nevertheless, ethical principles and identified risks are not enough on their own, they are useful for delineating the scope of the ethical inquiry and the areas concerned by the development of the AI system while also offering guidelines to follow, but a more structured approach needs to be put in place. That is where ethics-by-design emerges as a fundamental methodology:

- › **Ethical considerations** derived from the identified risks are integrated in the development process
- › Ethical considerations are translated in **requirements** guiding developers in their work, as well as into **assessment criteria** for the final evaluation
- › Several iterations might be performed in a feedback loop

⁹ <https://www.who.int/activities/ensuring-ethical-standards-and-procedures-for-research-with-human-beings>

- › Risks, requirements and assessment criteria are adjusted through reiteration
- › A final evaluation assesses the **ethical impacts** of the AI system developed

In this way, **requirements represent the norms and the normative guardrails within which the system acts, a moral imperative to follow, while assessment criteria reflect them.** More precisely, requirements delineate the ethical parameters and constraints that are informed by ethical principles and moral values. They influence decisions regarding the system architecture, the design of the algorithm, the data collection and its processing, and the interactions with human agents. Moreover, requirements serve as a basis on which to continuously compare with the established assessment criteria the behaviour of the system during the development cycle, adapting it at each new iteration if new ethical risks and shortcomings are introduced, also reflecting on the challenges that these poses.

Once the model runs its conclusive iterations, final evaluations are formulated that are important in identifying the impacts that an artificial intelligence system may have once it is introduced into a real-life scenario, and thus on society as a whole.

Figure 7 - outline of the ETHAI model

While the ethics-by-design methodology, especially the EdB-AI, is a crucial component for the assessment of an AI system, ensuring that potential harms and an ethical behaviour is respected, it may not be sufficient. As outlined in the preceding paragraph, principles such as the EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and the four principles of bioethics are practical operative principles that lack a proper value foundation.

This is where **Ethics of Care is integrated in the ETHAI model**, bridging the gap between principles and values, and between values and true, situated human beings. As already presented in section 2.2.4 of the present deliverable, ethics of care is able to acknowledge the diverse needs of individuals in different contexts, trying to critically deepen the understanding of controversies that arise in the development of a technology. This is even more true if we look at the core of its reflection, that is centred in human relationships: **adding care in the design of a technology, and in particular in the design of an AI system, allows to tackle in the discussion aspects and actors that otherwise would not be represented.** For example vulnerable users marginalised by these developments within this approach become an integral, if not central, part of the project; power dynamics inside the development are mitigated and equally balanced; ambiguities of morally complex situations created by the system are disambiguated for a more conscious ethical decision-making of all the stakeholders involved (e.g. trade off of values). This is done making a conscious and capillary work of **considering, for each risk and requirement, the effect it would**

have on those actors and factors, asking relevant questions and extracting with this approach relevant requirements and mitigation actions.

In conclusion, the **ETHAI is a model that can embody different values and principles** by combining and intertwining them to resolve complex ethical issues, thus giving a holistic view of all the processes of the development of an AI system. In this way, **the ETHAI informs individual decisions and actions by entering in the development and implementation stages, where developers, researchers and ethicist co-create the technology, thus ensuring that ethical considerations are coded inside it, while also representing a meta-structure of ethics with guidelines and specific requirements for the entire project and not merely an add-on or a separate process.** What ETHAI brings over and above other models and frameworks is its **flexibility**, having no predefined values and principles and adapting them to various fields of study, by deeply taking into account the context of application and the stakeholders involved.

In the next section, the depicted model will be applied to the use case of the MES-CoBraD project, to give a complete view of the process that characterizes the ETHAI.

3.3 THE INSTANTIATION OF THE ETHAI MODEL IN MES-COBRA D

During the MES-CoBraD project, the ETHAI model has evolved itself by following the research and development process, in particular some aspects of it sprint from the parts of the project that concern the creation of the MES-CoBraD platform and Expert System and the clinical trials, subsumed under the four PUCs and in part evaluated. This has allowed to refine the methodology underlying the ETHAI, confronting diverse ethical theories, principles, unprecedented new regulations (see the AI Act example), frameworks for the application of ethics and last but not least the creation of new standards in this field of study.

The role of the ETHAI is to provide and integrate ethical criteria throughout the technology development lifecycle, following an ethics-by-design approach. From the initial design phase through the assessment and evaluation of AI components, ETHAI acknowledges and addresses potential ethical challenges that may arise as development progresses towards deployment. However, coming at the end of the project and being one of its final outcomes, the ETHAI Model in the MES-CoBraD context will act as a tool for the assessment phase, based on the risk analysis and the definition of assessment criteria.

One of the objectives of the ETHAI model is to **foresight ethical risks and assess them in order to provide a clear understanding of what to expect during the development of an AI system in a particular context of application.**

This proposed organisation of risks will be the basis on which to evaluate the two final PUCs (3 and 4 in D2.8), and it represents an iteration of the ETHAI model. Given the early stages of the project during the evaluation of the first two PUCs (1 and 2), this iteration of the ETHAI model on the PUCs #3 and #4 sets an advancement of research.

Final **recommendations** will be provided for future developments of the technology, as to ascertain that ethics will continue to be included in the implementation of AI technology.

Figure 8 - The MES-CoBraD's ETHAI phases

The above image exemplifies the application of the **process at the basis of ETHAI model for MES-CoBraD**, therefore every phase has a precise scope that is related to a specific WP of the project:

- › In **WP2**, the identification of a specific ethics framework (D2.1; D2.3) for the development of an AI system in the healthcare domain is performed and principles are chosen.
- › In **WP3**, principles are implemented through **ethics-by-design** and a constant monitoring of the development accompanies regular **cross-WPs scientific meetings**.
- › **WP5** and **WP6** components in the **PUCs 3 and 4** will be assessed by using the ETHAI model.

The above-described process requires that a **mixed team of ethicists, clinician and developers** works together to correctly identify how the different issues are faced and derive eventual mitigation actions if necessary. Therefore, there will be **no “automatic” score resulting from the evaluation**. Rather, **a report will be generated**, with possible actions to perform in order to ensure the assessment criteria respect. The report will also be a **guideline to the ES users** (the clinicians) to know where the (eventual) shortcomings of the system may lie and take them into account.

4 MES-COBRA D EXPERT SYSTEM RISK ASSESSMENT

As defined in 2.2, the approach adopted by MES-CoBraD is based on the combination of the EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI criteria and the so-called “four principles of bioethics” (*Autonomy/Respect, Beneficence, Non Maleficence and Justice*), completed by the Ethics of Care approach. Accordingly with the AI Act, those elements will be used for a risk assessment tool.

4.1 THE ETHAI RISK ASSESSMENT MODEL

When defining a model for the ethical design and assessment of an AI system, the first action – also in line with the approach called upon by the AI act – should be to **identify and assess the ethical risks** that that system may generate. This is essential also to define assessment criteria: each requirement should answer to an identified risk and should be capable of mitigating it.

There are many risk assessment models for AI (also the AI act, discussed before, can be classified as one).

Borrowing the useful classification made by the OECD (OECD, 2023) one fundamental difference between the different risk assessment frameworks for AI can be identified in the scope itself of the different frameworks. Some (like the **OECD DDG**) are more focused on business relationships, others (like **ISO 31000**) take into account the organizations as a whole and some (like **HUDERIA**) mainly target human rights, democracy and fundamental freedoms. Another important aspect of a risk assessment framework (as highlighted in (Xia et al., 2023)) is which principles are addressed, who are the stakeholders and how are the AI risks assessed.

The **ETHAI model works as a risk assessment framework**, that **starting from the risks identification move on to the definition of a set of assessment criteria that make the system capable of mitigating those risks, while respecting the core ethical principles that have been put at the basis of the framework.**

Within the landscape of AI risk assessment frameworks, it certainly has similarities with the **HUDERIA** framework (Leslie et al., 2022) insofar as it aspires to cover all the phases of an AI project development (so it’s capable of acting not only ex post, as a mere assessment tool, but has a role also in the needs inception and design phase) and it has at its core the assessment of the respect of fundamental human rights.

As defined in 4.2, the MES-CoBraD risk assessment process is composed by 3 main steps that combine principles and values to assess the project AI-technology.

4.2 THE ETHAI RISK ASSESSMENT PROCESS

Step 1: The analysis of the nature of the AI system being developed, of the context, of the stakeholders, of the issues and of the ethical and legal principles (that should precede a proper risk assessment) has been made throughout the entire project in diverse phases, each reported in a separate deliverable (identification of ethical and legal framework in deliverable D2.1 and D2.3, stakeholders identification in deliverable D3.7, analysis of the desirable characteristics of AI system in D6.1, technical requirements and architecture in D7.1).

Step 2: Since this model builds on the foundations of the **EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI**, the **risks will be in first instance identified and classified under its requirements** (namely, Human agency and oversight; Technical robustness and safety; Privacy and data governance; Transparency, Diversity; Non-discrimination and fairness; Environmental and societal well-being; Accountability).

Starting from a list of potential risks that might impact a certain Expert System identified by means of a literature review, the ones pertinent for MES-CoBraD are selected. So, each risk is **classified** according to its **applicability** to the MES-CoBraD project (low, medium, high) and to its **likelihood**, that it's here defined as the **probability** of the described occurrence to happen during the project (low, medium, high).

To make immediately visible the applicability and the likelihood, a colour system has been adopted, in the following way:

Applicability

LOW The risk is not applicable to the project	MEDIUM There may be certain aspects of the project that are impacted by the risk	HIGH The risk is completely in line with the project's scope
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Likelihood

LOW The probability for the risk to happen is extremely limited, it would come as a surprise that the risk occurred	MEDIUM There could be certain circumstances, that can be defined, in which the risk occurs	HIGH It is highly expectable that the risk occurs, the circumstances in which it may occur are also easily foreseeable
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Further on, within deliverable D2.8, the **impact** of each risk will be assessed as a combination of its applicability and of its likelihood. Of course, if a risk is not applicable to the project, its impact (on the project) will be null, even though considered in absolute terms it may be an extremely dangerous occurrence (this could be the case, for instance, of the risks for the environment, that in MES-CoBraD are not applicable, even though they are listed here to maintain the generality of the approach). On the opposite, if a risk's applicability to the project is high, the risk could have a great impact even though its likelihood is a medium one. After having assessed the potential impact of a risk in this way, the effective impact is defined taking also into account the partners' views on that particular risk (a certain risk could have applicability and likelihood high, but still have not so high an impact depending on how its severity is considered by the project stakeholders) in deliverable D2.8 (final PUC assessment), after the MES-CoBraD's ES has been completed and experimented in clinical setting.

Step 3: After having identified and classified the risks under the EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI categories, a **further categorisation is made**, to accommodate them under the identified bioethics principles that lie at the core of the MES-CoBraD ethical framework and of the ETHAI model. Those will be **the four principles of bioethics to which the "care" has been added**, not properly a principle but a value. As extensively outlined in section 2.2, care cannot be treated as a principle but more as a sort of guiding light that should orientate moral choices. This is the reason why it is the core value alongside with the four principles of bioethics to be analysed, to complement the evaluation action on the risks posed by the Artificial Intelligence system. Therefore, the identified risks are re-categorized on the four principles of bioethics plus care.

4.2.1 MES-COBRA D MAIN OPEN ETHICS ISSUES

This is part of Step 1 of the ETHAI risk assessment process, namely the analysis of the context. Part of it has already been performed in section 2.1 where an overview of the current debate on the ethical issues of AI as applied to healthcare as been given. Here some open questions related particularly to the MES-CoBraD project and to its field of application will be considered, some of which had already been discussed into the deliverable D2.5 and had been identified as emerging from and applying specifically

to the project. In particular, the following questions remained open:

- How can we be sure that there aren't hidden biases in the algorithm that compromise the fairness and equity of the results? How should clinicians decide to minimize this risk?
- How should the effectiveness of MES-CoBraD results be proven in order to reach a sufficient certainty that the outputs of the system are valid and not biased?
- Is it possible that conflicting ethics values (with respect to the ones the clinician adheres to or the Consortium adheres to) are inadvertently introduced into the algorithm, placing the clinician in a situation of moral conflict when he/she is presented a certain diagnosis by the system?
- If MES-CoBraD is used at scale, not by individuals but by governments, to decide about healthcare policies, the negative consequences generated by the risk of hidden biases would be even worse. How can they be mitigated?
- Is the clinician fully accountable if he/she bases his/her diagnosis on wrong or biased outputs?
- MES-CoBraD is designed on the basis of the Explainable AI (XAI) approach, but – especially when some techniques like deep learning, data augmentation or neural networks are used – the working of the algorithm is not totally accessible, and its outputs cannot be fully explainable. This conflicts with the principle of Autonomy and again poses a problem for the requisite of accountability. How can a clinician be deemed responsible for basing his/her decision on a diagnosis he/she CANNOT fully understand? And if the patient is to be considered as the ultimate subject of autonomy, how can his/her decisions be considered autonomous if they are based on opaque data and “reasoning”?
- Might there be a risk of depersonalization of care deriving from the introduction of the MES-CoBraD Expert System in the doctor/patient relationship?
- When transferring knowledge from human experts to the AI system, is there the risk that something gets lost? Is this something identifiable and quantifiable?

In addition, there are ethics issues of the application of AI to healthcare that are peculiar to the treatment of neurodegenerative disorders (Ienca & Ignatiadis, 2020). For instance, adopting a “computational psychiatry” approach might result in a biological reductionist stance, cutting out sociocultural factors or changes in conscious experience derived or associated with brain diseases (Wiese & Friston, 2022).

In other words, basing their work heavily on the outputs of a system that does not sufficiently consider socio/cultural as well as psychological factors, clinicians could adopt an approach to care that does not consider essential factors of brain illnesses and of their treatment, that are not solely biological.

Another risk is that concentrating the attention solely on the biological aspects of mental disorders increases the associated stigma and reduces the clinician empathy (Lebowitz & Ahn, 2014), which could obviously result in a damage for the patient, contrasting with the non-maleficence principle.

Furthermore, if used for predictive purposes (identifying the people more at risk of developing a certain complex brain disease), the system could target perfectly healthy people who in his “judgment” are at risk of developing such a disease, raising the following questions: Should the clinician let them know? Is greater the risk of being negatively influenced or the risk of developing a disease if not treated (Ursin et al., 2021)?

On the other hand, there's a risk of under-diagnosing, which can limit treatment options for individuals who are particularly susceptible to developing a complex brain disease.

More broadly, as (Ursin et al., 2021) point out, the choice is between two options: if AI is a mere tool, a “second opinion”, then it's not clear why one should bear all the costs and ethical risks of its implementation and use; if instead it effectively outperforms human doctors in terms of time and accuracy, not considering its advice could be considered “medical malpractice” if done by a human doctor.

Finally, given the progresses of AI as applied to neurosciences, sci-fi scenarios can be taken into account

that strongly question the people’s autonomy (the studies on deep brain stimulation and its ethical implications are a good example of this issue) and right to the privacy of their “mind”, opening risks of “disclosure of personal identity” that are far more real than one might imagine (Kellmeyer, 2019).

While some of the above issues will be directly translated into risks, all of them will be part of the assessment to be conducted in D2.8 at the end of the project lifetime, based on the ethics framework defined in the current deliverable.

4.2.2 IDENTIFICATION AND FIRST CLASSIFICATION OF MES-COBRA D RISKS

This represents Step 2 of the risk assessment process, based on the literature review and considering EU Guidelines for Trustworthy AI principles (with the exception of the impact assessment that will be done within deliverable D2.8).

4.2.2.1 Human agency and oversight

To identify risk factors related to human agency and oversight it was performed a desk-research but also exploited CEL previous work in the context of the project. In this sense it was already evident that one of the major risks is the loss of autonomy by the clinicians, not because the ES takes autonomous decisions (something that – at least in the present release of the platform – it will never do) but that clinicians may be subject to the so-called “automation bias” as they could unconsciously believe that everything that comes out of the algorithm is perforce correct and reliable, even better than what could come out of their own judgment and competence. Also, the contrary is possible of course: the clinicians are led to judge negatively anything that comes out of the algorithm and are inclined to reject otherwise valid results.

There is in fact another maybe subtler risk: to be sure that there is always a human supervision, a human supervisor is put in charge, but this human must be put in a position to completely and correctly understand and evaluate the system’s outputs. It is unfortunately realistic to imagine that the human supervisor may instead not understand the working of the algorithm, not have the necessary competences to evaluate its outputs, or be subject to the algorithmic aversion bias and so fail systematically, or even if the supervisor has all the necessary competences the system may not be designed in such a way as to be “capable” of correctly explaining its outputs. In each case, the result is either a loss of autonomy or an error deriving from the fear of autonomy loss.

Table 1 - Human agency and oversight risks

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
The clinician is subject to the automation bias	The clinician passively accepts everything that comes from the algorithm		
The clinician is subject to the luddism bias	The clinician refuses everything that comes from the algorithm		
There is a human overseer, but he/she lacks the competencies to form an accurate judgment over the working of the algorithm	The overseer fails to judge correctly and this results into damages		
The human clinician is overwhelmed by the algorithm and feel he/she cannot control it	The clinician loses trust in the algorithm, doesn't look for a correct cooperation		
A human is appointed to oversee the algorithm but	The human overseer is biased (not only for lack		

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
he/she systematically fails in judging the validity of its outputs	of competencies)		
A human is appointed to oversee the algorithm but lacks the time and/or receives pressure so he/she is not able to judge correctly	The algorithm is a time and money saving tool. It may happen that its adoption is improperly hastened		
A human is appointed to oversee but the control is just a “cosmetic” one, and no real assessment is made	The control is faced with superficiality, if the algorithm returns wrong results no one notices		
A human is appointed to oversee but he/she has no real authority over the adoption of algorithm’s outputs	There isn’t a clear chain of authority, the overseer sees the errors but cannot stop the process		
The clinician is not put in the position to understand and thus correctly evaluate the algorithm’s outputs as there isn’t an effective reporting and explanation system in place	The working of the system is not accessible, as no reporting and explanation system is available		
The patient is completely reduced to data, a full deterministic approach is adopted, evidence based medicine substitutes experience based one, the data becomes the doctor	The power of analysis of AI algorithm makes it relatively easy to see only the quantitative side of healthcare, causing a decay of medicine itself		
If AI system’s reasoning in unknowable, then no informed consent is possible. People lose their freedom of choice	Informed consent becomes a lie, bioethics principles are infringed		
Doctor becomes dependant on the algorithm, loses his diagnostic ability	Using more and more the AI system clinicians start relying on it till they are no more capable of doing without		
Patients treated as commodities and not as individuals	Patients, analyzed through the AI, are treated in the most economical way for healthcare providers, without considering their real needs		

4.2.2.2 Technical robustness and safety

Technical robustness pertains not only to the capacity of the system to not generate errors and technical

malfunctions, but also to how it is from the one hand protected from malicious attacks from the outside and from the other hand capable of adapting to the environment without losing its reliability and effectiveness. Also, the problem here is not only that the system works correctly (there are no errors) but also that – in case something happens – ways are built into the system to promptly and automatically identify problems and alert the relevant stakeholders, Last but not least, data loss due to technical malfunctioning and its consequences should be taken into account and avoided.

Table 2 - Technical robustness and safety risks

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
The system is vulnerable to cyberattacks	The system is breachable		
The system is not replicable	The system does not deliver the same results when using similar datasets		
The system is not robust	The system is not replicable in contexts and with datasets different from the original one		
Undetected system failures happen, there is no automated error reporting	No automated error reporting system has been put in place, any error must be painstakingly detected		
The system is vulnerable to adversarial attacks	The system is maliciously brought to behave in ways different than the ones it was conceived for		
The system is vulnerable to data breaches	Data are stolen or corrupted		
The system is not protected against critical data loss	Data are lost		
There isn't a log and permission system that allows to identify the origin of a malfunctioning	No log system has been implemented, it's impossible to know who used the system at a certain moment		

4.2.2.3 Privacy and data governance

There are objective risks related to data governance, especially sensitive data, and subjective risks, related to the mistrust effect generated by the possibility of data breaches and misuses. In fact, the concern related to personal data breaches and misuses is one of the main issues mentioned during every acceptance assessment and can be a powerful source of failure for any AI system, especially those that are to be used inside delicate contexts like the healthcare system (even though, particularly in healthcare, people is often more likely to be concerned about receiving a proper care than about the access and sharing of their personal data). Besides, personal data protection is one of the main points of the AI act and of every regulation about AI systems. It must be noted that the problem of personal data is much more extensive than the access to a certain set of data about a certain person: due to the massive access and use of data, a person can be re-identified, some of his/her traits can be inferred, his/her behaviour or attitudes can be derived, in some cases even from his/her physical characteristics. Fake content, including personal or even biometric data, can be generated and data can massively be used for

secondary purposes. Finally, personal data could be used for mass surveillance or social scoring purposes. Of course, some of these possibilities are prohibited by law, but the fact that they are prohibited does not mean that they are not possible. So, the risks related to this aspect must be attentively identified and assessed.

Table 3 - Privacy and data governance risks

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
Individuals re-identification through data combination	Even if personal data are anonymized, from a number of characteristics it is possible to re-identify a subject, posing his/her privacy at risk		
Creation of inferential information by the combination of multiple data sources about an individual	Information about individuals can be inferred linking divers characteristics		
Fake personal data and profiles generation	Fake AI generated profiles are generated or real people profiles are stolen		
Personal data repurposing (secondary usage)	Data gathered for a certain purpose are then re-used for a different purpose without telling the users		
Personal data is used for surveillance purposes	Personal data are used to identify individuals with the purpose of monitoring and tracking them		
Personal data is used for social scoring purposes	Individuals are classified according to their characteristics and those classifications are used to score them according to certain parameters (e.g. the probability of developing a certain illness)		
Mistrust is generated as a result of a lack of transparency about personal data usage	Stakeholders may perceive that they cannot access to the inner working of the algorithm and refuse to accept it as a consequence of a lack of trust		
Biometric data are subject to secondary usage resulting in a violation of human body	Biometric data are one of the most critical kinds of personal data, they can remain available after they have been used for the primary usage and be subject to multiple analyses and scrutiny, that can be assimilable to a violation of human body		

4.2.2.4 Transparency

Transparency is strictly related to autonomy (how can a patient or a clinician be autonomous if he/she is not put in the condition of understanding what is happening?), to accountability (can someone be considered truly accountable for something he/she cannot fully understand? How can responsibilities be

traced back if the working of the system is not accessible?), and of course, for obvious reasons, to trust. The respect of quality and ethical standards cannot be fully verified (only the final output can be judged, but not how the system arrived to it). Of course, systematic biases when present, may be extremely difficult to detect and to resolve. On the other hand, transparency, when achieved, can lead to other risks: it may be obtainable only at the price of a loss of accuracy and effectiveness, or at the risk of making the system more vulnerable to external attacks. The user – being in possess of loads of information – may experience an excessive responsibility burden, or his/her data may be exposed with more ease. Finally, the output of the system, albeit transparent, may be so complicated that no true transparency is achieved because only real experts can truly understand it. Having this in mind, the MES-CoBraD AI components are developed taking as a reference the explainable AI approach (as detailed in deliverable D6.2, section 2.5.4), having in mind that – especially in a medical system – having the means to deconstruct the processes of a system, not only for what pertains the operations performed by it, but also the understability of its results, is of paramount importance. Explainability in this sense becomes one of the fundamentals requisites of an AI system, summing up transparency (a system cannot be explainable if it isn't transparent), trustworthiness (if a system is not explainable, it cannot easily trusted or assessed), autonomy (if the way a system arrived at a certain decision cannot be understood, the outcomes can be only blind reject or blind reliance).

Table 4 - Transparency risks

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
The respect of decision making standards, ethical constraints, quality during the elaboration process cannot be verified	If the algorithm is not transparent, it is not possible to verify the respect of standards and constraints and there is the risk that they are violated		
Making systems transparent may expose personal or sensitive data	If the system is transparent, it may be more subject to data breaches or inadvertently make available personal and/or sensitive data		
If the system is transparent may be more subject to hacks and attacks	If the system is transparent, is transparent also for those who may have malicious intentions		
Algorithm's outputs can only be accepted or refused but not questioned, understood, ameliorated. Their accuracy and validity is not easily assessed	The algorithm acts as a black box, making difficult to assess the validity of its outputs and exposing users to the risk of biased or unreliable results		
ML systems cannot really be transparent and explainable. To make them transparent may mean to make them less accurate and effective.	A compromise must be reached between the effectiveness and the transparency. The most powerful ML learning algorithms do not manage to be really transparent, but of course this exposes to		

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
	the risk of biased or unreliable results		
Transparency may lead to place an excessive burden on the user, responsabilizing him too much	Rather than protecting the user designing an algorithm that has all the necessary safeguards the user is forced to control the working of the algorithm to defend himself. This deprives the developer of his responsibilities, unfairly discharging them on the user		
The system is transparent but nonetheless it's not understandable by the intended audience	The complexity is so high that users cannot understand the working of the system and cannot assess the validity of its outputs		
Lack of transparency may decrease trust in the system	If intended users do not trust the system they may not use it in the correct way or be subject to the luddism bias		

4.2.2.5 Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness

One of the major risks of AI systems, especially when applied into healthcare, is the presence of undetected biases (originating from many different factors: for a list of the types of possible biases please see D2.3) that lead to systematic error and inaccuracy, and in the worst cases to discrimination and unfair distribution of benefits and/or burdens. The most part of the risks in this category is due to an uneven and unfair group composition during (clinical) studies: when the algorithm is trained on datasets deriving from those groups, it will learn “wrong” things and return biased outputs. Also, the opposite is possible: the algorithm is applied to a completely different context than the one that originated the training dataset, something that may result in outcomes similar to those taken into account in the case of unbalanced group composition.

Table 5 - Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness risks

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
The system discriminates against or fosters certain social or demographic groups	As a result of biased training datasets or of a faulty algorithmic design a systematic unwanted and possibly undetected discrimination against certain groups (social, demographic, gender, etc) emerges		
The system returns a uniform view of the human beings, without taking into account	Personalized medicine means taking into account individual differences, while an AI system, if not adequately		

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
diversities	designed, may flatten the approach on a standardized vision of health and human beings		
The system is not capable of working correctly in contexts different than the native one	If applied to a different context the system may not work correctly returning incorrect results		
The system regularly delivers wrong or biased results, due to a not correctly balanced training dataset	Systematic mistakes or inaccuracies are generated and possibly not detected, damaging the users		
The system – due to wrong evaluations - worsens the access to the healthcare system	If the system is used to evaluate the effectiveness of healthcare policies at national or regional level there may be the risk that this results in the unfair discrimination or exclusion or restriction of the access to the healthcare system of groups or individuals		
A system is developed centered on the needs of a small privileged portion of population	If the training dataset is not truly representative of the target population and the system is designed not taking into account all the possible stakeholders there is the risk that it does not represents the needs of the target population but of a small portion of it		
The system worsens the health disparity in low resource settings	AI systems are sophisticated and expensive tools, that also require an extensive training and knowledge to be used correctly. There may be the risk that their potentialities are available only to sites that are already advantaged and wealthy, thus worsening the general health disparities		
The system does not take into account the needs and point of view of underrepresented, fragile groups, such as people with disabilities	Being designed without taking into account all the stakeholders and in particular people with special needs or disabilities the system is not able to correctly respond to their needs or		

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
	discriminates against them excluding them altogether or returning incorrect outputs		

4.2.2.6 Environmental and societal well-being

AI systems can have a huge impact on society and on the environment, some of which not particularly evident. For example, water usage may be a problem (in large AI systems water is used for cooling, and water especially in certain places is a scarce resource) as well as that of energy consumption by LLMs.

However, the possible negative societal consequences of the use of AI systems are much wider than this, and spread from impact on labour to malicious uses (for instance on purpose disinformation or misinformation), from systematic discrimination of certain social groups to unequal distribution of AI generated wealth. In fact, it is having these problems in mind that within the AI act certain AI systems are prohibited. Some of these risks do not apply to MES-CoBraD and to similar systems but as the ETHAI wants to achieve a general view on this topic they have been included here, nonetheless.

Table 6 - Environmental and societal well-being risks

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
AI systems may determine a huge power consumption	Certain kinds of AI systems (e.g. LLMs) need huge power supplies to work, determining a possible consumption of scarce resources (energy) and related costs	■	■
Water consumption for cooling purposes	Water especially in certain settings is a scarce resource. Using for AI systems may result in having less of it available for human consumption purposes	■	■
Catastrophic consequences in case of malfunctioning of AI controlled systems (e.g. dams, nuclear power plants)	If an AI system acts controls a critical infrastructure, its failure could have dramatic consequences	■	■
Systematic unwanted discrimination of certain social groups	If the algorithm is biased as a consequence of a not properly balanced dataset	■	■
Large scale disinformation, misinformation or manipulation campaigns	An AI system, thanks to its capacity to analyse huge quantities of data, can be used to manipulate information and purposefully generate misinformation and deceptive information, with manipulative purposes	■	■

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
Impact on labour, mass unemployment	AI systems may substitute human work in many fields, also the creative or knowledge intensive ones		
Uneven distribution of AI derived wealth and advantages	AI systems, being expensive, may be available only to a small portion of the population, that – with taxes – could on the other hand sustain part of the related costs		
Malicious use (e.g. new AI engineered weapons or pandemics, mass surveillance, social scoring, civil liberties infringement)	AI technology could be used for many malicious purposes thanks to its immense data analysis and manipulation capacity		

4.2.2.7 Accountability

Finally, accountability in the era of the advent of artificial intelligence is a big issue, as it becomes blurred the line between who should be deemed responsible for a certain thing (a decision, an error, an action) and who shouldn't. The responsibility is divided between machine and humans, and as many could be identified as accountable for a certain outcome (the designers, the developers, the controllers, the algorithm itself, the users...) if a damage occurs (and this in the sanitary field is even more relevant) it isn't easy to trace back the accountability line and asking for redress may be difficult, if not impossible.

On the other hand, if this line of argumentation is taken too far, it could generate a sort of “defensive” engineering, where everyone, instead of doing the best possible job, tries to defend him/herself from the possible inclusion into the “accountability chain”.

Table 7 - Accountability risks

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
Balkanization of accountability: the accountability is heavily distributed between many actors (both human and artificial) and is not possible to detect a single agent who can be deemed responsible	There isn't a clear responsibility chain, it's impossible to allocate responsibilities, the result is that no one is truly accountable		
If the producer is not responsible for errors or malfunctioning of the algorithm, he may not put the necessary effort to make it in the appropriate way	The risk is that not having to answer for possible incorrect results the producer do not puts all the necessary effort in the system design and development, delivering a not optimized system		
If the producer is too much responsible, he may be frightened and revert to “defensive” engineering, aiming ad defend himself	The system may be slowed down or underperform due to “defensive” strategies adopted by the producer, who will be prone to reduce		

Risk factor	Explanation	Applicability inside MES-CoBraD	Likelihood inside MES-CoBraD
rather than doing the best possible work	the scope of the system to be sure that it is not prone to errors		
A human in the loop is introduced as scapegoat, only for cosmetic purposes	The presence of a human in the loop gives a false sense of security that results in not paying the due attention to possible biases, errors, malfunctionings	■	■
Is not possible to trace a clear accountability chain, if a damage occurs it's not possible to ask for appropriate redress	Damaged persons are not able to obtain redress and compensation for the damage they suffered	■	■
Lack of trust deriving from lack of accountability	People do not want to use the system or that the system is used, generating a loss of money and of possibilities of ameliorating results or processes in the field where the system should have been applied	■	■

4.2.3 RE-CATEGORISATION OF IDENTIFIED RISKS

The above relevant identified risks (the ones with red and the orange flags) are classified under the four principles of bioethics plus care ethics (Step 3 of the risk assessment process), that represent the ethical foundation of the MES-CoBraD ETHAI. In this way it will be possible to use the identified risks to outline the ethical assessment criteria that will represent both the design and the assessment guideline of the ETHAI model as applied to the MES-CoBraD project. This operation is made for the sake of clarity and to put in perfect correspondence the various phases of the ethical assessment of the project. At the same time, it makes extremely clear if something is missing for example at the care ethics level, in case none of the risks outlined under each of the EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (AI HLEG) categories properly fit into an ethics of care framework. This is why it is so important to complement the classic principlist approach with a care ethics one, because doing otherwise would make us blind to other existing and different risks.

Respect for persons

Table 8 - Respect for persons risks

AI HLEG category	Risk
Human agency and oversight	The clinician is subject to the automation bias
	The clinician is subject to the luddism bias
	There is a human overseer, but he/she lacks the competencies to form an accurate judgment over the working of the algorithm
	The human clinician is overwhelmed by the algorithm and feel he/she cannot control it
	A human is appointed to oversee the algorithm but he/she systematically fails in judging the validity of its outputs
	A human is appointed to oversee the algorithm but lacks the time and/or receives pressure so he/she is not able to judge correctly

AI HLEG category	Risk
	A human is appointed to oversee but the control is just a “cosmetic” one, and no real assessment is made
	A human is appointed to oversee but he/she has no real authority over the adoption of algorithm’s outputs
	The clinician is not put in the position to understand and thus correctly evaluate the algorithm’s outputs as there isn’t an effective reporting and explanation system in place
Privacy and data governance	Individuals re-identification
	Creation of inferential information by the combination of multiple data sources about an individual
	Fake personal data and profiles generation
	Data combination and individuals identification
	Personal data repurposing (secondary usage)
	Personal data is used for surveillance purposes
	Personal data is used for social scoring purposes
	Biometric data are subject to secondary usage resulting in a violation of human body
Transparency	The respect of decision-making standards, ethical constraints, quality during the elaboration process cannot be verified
	The algorithm’s outputs can only be accepted or refused but not questioned, understood, ameliorated. Their accuracy and validity is not easily assessed
	ML systems may not really be transparent and explainable. To make them transparent may mean to make them less accurate and effective.
	Transparency may lead to place an excessive burden on the user, responsabilizing him too much
	The system is transparent but nonetheless it’s not understandable by the intended audience
Environmental and societal well being	Large scale disinformation, misinformation or manipulation campaigns
	Malicious use (e.g. new AI engineered weapons or pandemics, mass surveillance, social scoring, civil liberties infringement)
Accountability	A human in the loop is introduced as scapegoat, only for cosmetic purposes
	Is not possible to trace a clear accountability chain, if a damage occurs it’s not possible to ask for appropriate redress

Beneficence

Table 9 - Beneficence risks

AI HLEG category	Risk
Technical robustness and safety	The system is not replicable
	The system is not robust
Privacy and data governance	Personal data repurposing (secondary usage)
	Personal data is used for surveillance purposes
	Biometric data are subject to secondary usage resulting in a violation of human body
Diversity, non-discrimination and	The system returns a uniform view of the human beings, without taking

AI HLEG category	Risk
fairness	into account diversities
	The system – due to wrong evaluations - worsens the access to the healthcare system
Environmental and societal well being	Systematic unwanted discrimination of certain social groups
	Uneven distribution of AI derived wealth and advantages
Accountability	Is not possible to trace a clear accountability chain, if a damage occurs it's most possible to ask for appropriate redress

Non Maleficence

Table 10 - Non maleficence risks

AI HLEG category	Risk
Human agency and oversight	The clinician is subject to the automation bias
	There is a human overseer, but he/she lacks the competencies to form an accurate judgment over the working of the algorithm
	A human is appointed to oversee the algorithm but he/she systematically fails in judging the validity of its outputs
	A human is appointed to oversee the algorithm but lacks the time and/or receives pressure so he/she is not able to judge correctly
	A human is appointed to oversee but he/she doesn't fulfil its role correctly and the control is superficial, so no real assessment is made
Technical robustness and safety	The system is vulnerable to cyberattacks
	The system is not robust
	Undetected system failures happen, there is no automated error reporting
	The system is vulnerable to adversarial attacks
	The system is vulnerable to data breaches
	The system is not protected against critical data loss
	There isn't a log and permission system that allows to identify the origin of a malfunctioning, in case it is introduced into the system after its release
	The system is not able to ensure the validity and reliability of its outputs in presence of normal variations of the clinical environment
	The system is not able to correctly assign a reliability measure to its outputs
	A periodic test plan – to be done against preliminary defined metrics – does not exist or is not performed
	There is no automated reporting and alert system that is able to detect malfunctioning
	The test plan does not include patients, care givers and clinicians
	The test plan does not include diverse groups of people losing the possibility of accounting for different point of views and competencies
Privacy and data governance	Personal data repurposing (secondary usage)
	Personal data is used for surveillance purposes
	Biometric data are subject to secondary usage resulting in a violation of human body
	Individuals re-identification
	Fake personal data and profiles generation
	Data combination and individuals identification

AI HLEG category	Risk
Transparency	Personal data is used for social scoring purposes
	No data access protocols are put in place, access to data is unrestricted
	The respect of decision making standards, ethical constraints, quality during the elaboration process cannot be verified
	Making systems transparent may expose personal or sensitive data
	If the system is transparent may be more subject to hacks and attacks
Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness	The system does not have a way of reporting Data sets, data labelling and algorithms used in each step
	There isn't any accessible documentation
	The system returns a uniform view of the human beings, without taking into account diversities
	The system – due to wrong evaluations - worsens the access to the healthcare system
	The system discriminates against or fosters certain social or demographic groups
	The system is not capable of working correctly in contexts different than the native one
	The system regularly delivers wrong or biased results, due to a not correctly balanced training dataset
	The system is not designed involving all the relevant stakeholders categories, resulting in an output not representative of all the stakeholders' needs and demands
	The system cannot be used by anyone, regardless of their age, gender, abilities, characteristics or condition
	There isn't any way to ask for expert advice about functioning and use of the system
Environmental and societal well being	Systematic unwanted discrimination of certain social groups
	Uneven distribution of AI derived wealth and advantages
	Catastrophic consequences in case of malfunctioning of AI controlled systems (e.g. dams, nuclear power plants)
	Systematic unwanted discrimination of certain social groups
	Large scale disinformation, misinformation or manipulation campaigns
	Impact on labour, mass unemployment
Accountability	Malcious use (e.g. new AI engineered weapons or pandemics, mass surveillance, social scoring, civil liberties infringement)
	Is not possible to trace a clear accountability chain, if a damage occurs it's not possible to ask for appropriate redress

Justice

Table 11 - Justice risks

AI HLEG category	Risk
Human agency and oversight	A human is appointed to oversee but the control is just a “cosmetic” one, and no real assessment is made
Technical robustness and safety	The system is not replicable
	The system is not robust
Privacy and data governance	Personal data repurposing (secondary usage)

AI HLEG category	Risk
	Personal data is used for surveillance purposes
	Personal data is used for social scoring purposes
Transparency	Transparency may lead to place an excessive burden on the user, responsabilizing him too much
Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness	The system discriminates against or fosters certain social or demographic groups
	The system is not capable of working correctly in contexts different than the native one
	The system regularly delivers wrong or biased results, due to a not correctly balanced training dataset
	The system – due to wrong evaluations - worsens the access to the healthcare system
Environmental and societal well being	AI systems may determine a huge power consumption
	Water consumption for cooling purposes
	Systematic unwanted discrimination of certain social groups
	Impact on labour, mass unemployment
	Uneven distribution of AI derived wealth and advantages
Accountability	Balkanization of accountability: the accountability is heavily distributed between many actors (both human and artificial) and is not possible to detect a single agent who can be deemed responsible

Care

Table 12 - Care risks

AI HLEG category	Risk
Human agency and oversight	Some voices are being silenced during the design and development of the algorithm and afterwards when it is used
	Not enough attention is placed on the involvement of all the different stakeholders and their point of view is not listened to
	There is a human assessor but he/she evaluates the algorithm only on the basis of its performance (accuracy, efficacy, etc) and not on its holistic effect on the care relationship
	External factors, other than the true patients' needs, guide the development of the system. This results into a system that does not meet patients' needs and that might also be in conflict with them
	The effect of the emotional component on the efficacy of a therapeutic plan is completely overlooked, but in human beings is instead a fundamental component of the therapeutic plan's success (or failure)
	The use of AI opens the route to early diagnosis: an accurate balance must be reached between the potential risks generated by communicating an early diagnosis to the patient and the risks of not communicating it. The correct way of dealing with this matter can only be found on the basis of non-deterministic, non-algorithmic considerations
	The system is not designed and tested taking into account the patients' needs and feedback
Technical robustness and safety	The context on which the algorithm's conclusions are based is not considered as a fundamental part of the decision making process
Privacy and data governance	Vulnerabilities are not protected but rather are exploited to achieve results that are external to the patient's interests

AI HLEG category	Risk
	Patients' needs and point of views are overshadowed by aspects like the formal respect of rules and regulations
Transparency	The patient is overloaded with too much information and an excessive responsibility is placed on him/her
	A paternalistic attitude is adopted with the patient that is deprived of the information necessary to understand and participate in the proposed therapeutic process
Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness	The system is designed in such a way that eliminates the possibility of taking into account the needs and protected classes, people at risk of social exclusion, fragile or marginalized stakeholders
	The system returns a uniform view of the human beings, without taking into account diversities
	A biological deterministic attitude is adopted, not considering factors that are essential to the human beings, especially in the healthcare and even more in brain diseases field
	Only technological parameters (e.g. system robustness) are considered during the design and development phase, bringing to neglect fundamental aspects proper of a care relationship
Environmental and societal well being	The interdependence relationships (at the individual and the societal level) are not considered during the design phase of the system, opening the possibility to a complete neglect of them during its usage
Accountability	Patients do not have reference points, if the responsibility chain is not clear they may feel that no one is really taking care of them and that they are left alone, losing trust and having consequences on the efficacy of healthcare program

5 MES-COBRA D ASSESSMENT CRITERIA FOR ETHICAL AI

While the preceding sections described the ethical stance and framework that the project intends to adopt, a risk assessment analysis based on that framework and a general description of the model, the next subsections will describe how the model will be applied: it will provide a list of assessment criteria that the system should comply with in order to deliver outputs that are ethically acceptable.

Those assessment criteria will be used for the project final assessment that will be part of D2.8.

Taking into account the context of MES-CoBraD and the technology TRL, **only relevant assessment criteria will be applied. Therefore, the list of assessment criteria in the current deliverable is a sub-set of potential assessment criteria for an ES system.**

5.1 THE MES-CoBRAD ETHICS ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

In this section a series of assessment criteria will be outlined to respond and mitigate the identified risks. Those criteria are classified based on the four bioethical principles plus the Care value. For each of those classes, the EU Guidelines for Trustworthy AI principles are applied.

5.1.1 RESPECT FOR PERSONS

Table 13 - Respect for persons assessment criteria

Req #ID	Identified Risk	MES-CoBraD Criterium
Human agency and oversight		
RH1	There is no control over the working of the algorithm, unwanted or unexpected results may occur as a result without any means to mitigate them. Humans involved in the process may feel they are overcome and overrun by something they do not control and/or understand	With the aim of empowering human beings, the ES should support human autonomy, thus enabling informed and autonomous decision-making that respects human agency. Therefore, Human in the Loop and Human in Command mechanisms shall be implemented
RH2		The human clinician shall be able to direct the working of the ES by selecting certain data sets or certain variables as well as the necessary skills to use it
RH3		The output must be readable and explainable for an effective understanding of the human clinician in charge.
RH4		The ultimate decision about a certain diagnosis or care proposal shall always be taken by the human clinician.
Privacy and data governance		
RP1	The matter of data protection other than being a legal obligation is also an ethical affair: personal data may be used for purposes other than the ones declared or there may be unexpected and unforeseen results deriving from their recollection and usage	Personal data of patients shall be protected to avoid any possible inappropriate use and any damage deriving from it. The system shall be compliant with the GDPR and with any further regulations of the countries in which it will be used
RP2		Personal data must not be used for surveillance or social scoring purposes
RP3		The patients shall be given a detailed explanation of what is done with their data and of the purpose of the data collection. Only the strict necessary data shall be asked to the patients. If the patient wants to withdraw its consent, it shall be extremely clear how to do that and how to request that his/her data are cancelled
Transparency		

Req #ID	Identified Risk	MES-CoBraD Criterium
RT1	The system may become a “black box” whose outputs must then be accepted “by faith”. If they are wrong, there isn’t way of detecting it. Both the clinician and the patient are then deprived of a true faculty of choice	The data on the basis of which certain decisions are taken shall be accessible by the clinician
RT2		The way in which the algorithm arrived at a certain decision or diagnosis shall be accessible by the clinician
RT3		Design choices and the architecture of the system shall be documented and accessible to users and policy makers
Accountability		
RA1	With the introduction of the AI the chain of responsibility may be lost, it is not clear who is accountable for a wrong diagnosis. The clinician is brought to accept the output of the system as an authority, but if it is wrong it is he who is responsible and in the worst cases who is going to pay for it. The patient feels unsafe and doesn’t know how to obtain justice	It shall be made clear to the patient that the diagnosis or the care program is partially made on the basis of the working of an ES as well as who is responsible for the outcomes
RA2		A tracking mechanism shall be implemented to log accesses and actions carried out by using the system

5.1.2 BENEFICENCE

Table 14 - Beneficence assessment criteria

Req #ID	Identified Risk	MES-CoBraD Criterium
Technical robustness and safety		
BT1	The AI system is developed without sufficient technical requisites for safety	The system should be robust and replicable
Environmental and societal well being		
BS1	The system development can perpetuate discrimination of certain social groups and distribute wealth and advantages of research only to certain groups, thus delimiting access in healthcare	The AI system should not discriminate systematically certain social groups

5.1.3 NON MALEFICENCE

Table 15 - Non maleficence assessment criteria

Req #ID	Identified Risk	MES-CoBraD Criterium
Human agency and oversight		
NH1	There is no control over the working of the algorithm, unwanted or unexpected results	The human overseer tasked with monitoring the algorithm must possess the necessary information to accurately assess its functioning, as well as the ability to identify any potential errors or

Req #ID	Identified Risk	MES-CoBraD Criterium
	may occur as a result without any means to mitigate them. Humans involved in the process may feel overcome and overrun by something they do not control and/or understand	biases present within the system.
NH2		The system must facilitate effective oversight by providing tools and support (e.g. reporting system, complete list of datasets etc.) to the human appointed for assessing the validity of algorithm outputs, reducing the likelihood of systematic failures in judgment
NH3		The human overseeing the algorithm must have adequate time and resources to thoroughly evaluate algorithms outputs, free from external pressures or constraints, to ensure accurate judgment and decision-making.
NH4		Provide a checklist to the human in charge of the oversight of the system to ensure that at least the minimum control is done
NH5		Provide a checklist to the human in charge of the oversight of the system to ensure that at least the minimum control is done
Technical Robustness and safety		
NT1	If a diagnostic system is implemented that relies on MES-CoBraD ES a system failure, especially if undetected, may bring many negative consequences: the inability to access data, the inability to deliver a diagnosis, wrong diagnosis and consequently wrong therapies	The system must be designed and implemented to achieve robustness, with public performance parameters and measures in place to withstand unexpected failures, disruptions, or adverse conditions without compromising its overall functionality and performance.
NT2		The system must implement stringent measures of safeguards against attacks and data breaches, with regular security assessments to identify and address vulnerabilities. A fallback plan should be implemented
NT3		The system must establish comprehensive backup and recovery procedures to protect critical data from loss, ensuring that essential information remains accessible and intact in the event of a system failure or disaster.
NT4		The system must incorporate a robust logging and permission system to track and monitor system activities, allowing for the identification of any anomalies or malfunctions introduced into the system post-release, enabling effective troubleshooting and remediation efforts
NT5		The system should be able to assign and report reliability measures together with its outputs
NT6		Periodic test plans must be established and performed against preliminary defined metrics
NT7		The test plans must include patients, care givers and clinicians
NT8		Periodic tests should include diverse groups of people in order to include different competences, points of view and perspectives
NT9		Periodic tests should include diverse groups of people in order to include different competences, points of view and perspectives
Privacy and data governance		
NP1	If personal data of participants – and in particular health data - are disclosed, they can be used for profiling purposes and at the worst	Biometric data collected by the system must be strictly restricted to their primary usage, with clear guidelines prohibiting any secondary usage that may result in violations of individuals' bodily integrity or privacy rights.

Req #ID	Identified Risk	MES-CoBraD Criterium
NP2	also for social scoring purposes, without individuals even know that	The system must implement measures to prevent the re-identification of individuals from anonymised or pseudonymised data, safeguarding their privacy and confidentiality.
NP3		Data combination and individuals' identification within the system must adhere to strict privacy protocols, with safeguards in place to protect against unauthorized access or misuse of personal information.
NP4		Data access protocols shall be put in place defining who can access data and under which circumstances
NP5		Data access protocols shall be put in place defining who can access data and under which circumstances
Transparency		
NTR1	If the working of the system and its datasets are inaccessible, there is no way to verify the correctness of its outputs.	when making systems transparent the system must prioritise the protection of personal and sensitive data, implementing robust privacy measures to safeguard against unauthorised access or exposure
NTR2		Mitigate the increased vulnerability to hacks and attacks that may result from increased transparency, ensuring the security and integrity of the system and its data.
NTR3		Data sets, data labelling and algorithms used in each step shall be documented,
NTR4		Data sets, data labelling and algorithms used in each step shall be documented,
Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness		
ND1	AI systems in healthcare are the potential source of misuses and discriminatory behaviour and outcomes	The system's training dataset must be balanced regularly to mitigate the risk of delivering wrong or biased results, ensuring that its outputs are reliable, unbiased, and reflective of real-world diversity.
ND2		There shall be a way for users of the system to ask for help or advice about the functioning and use of the ES and to provide feedback (e.g., to report bugs or poor performance or biases and/or discrimination issues arising from its use)
ND3		There shall be a way for users of the system to ask for help or advice about the functioning and use of the ES and to provide feedback (e.g., to report bugs or poor performance or biases and/or discrimination issues arising from its use)
ND4		Prevent systematic discrimination against any social groups, ensuring that all individuals are treated fairly and equally regardless of their demographic characteristics.
Environmental and societal well being		
NE1	The system may deliver unattended outputs or perpetuate errors systematically, thus producing inequalities that impact users and society as a whole	The system must be used only as a decision support system, but never as a substitute of a human doctor
NE2		

5.1.4 JUSTICE

Table 16 - Justice assessment criteria

Req #ID	Identified Risk	MES-CoBraD Criterium
Technical robustness and safety		
JT1	Absence of specific technical requisites means absence of safety or robustness for the system. The system is not verifiable, and vulnerabilities can be exploited by malicious actors	The system must undergo rigorous testing and validation processes to ensure robustness, demonstrating resilience to various conditions, inputs, and potential failures while maintaining its intended functionalities and performance standards.
JT2		The system must undergo rigorous testing and validation processes to ensure robustness, demonstrating resilience to various conditions, inputs, and potential failures while maintaining its intended functionalities and performance standards.
Privacy and data governance		
JP1	Absence of specific privacy measures means absence of privacy for the user and a good data governance mechanism. The system and the data and the users are vulnerable to manipulation	The system must strictly prohibit the repurposing of personal data for secondary usage, ensuring that data collected is solely utilised for its original intended purpose and in compliance with relevant privacy regulations.
Transparency		
JTR1	Absence of transparencies means absence of auditability and impossibility of spotting possible sources of biases and discrimination	The way in which the algorithm arrived at a certain decision or diagnosis shall be accessible by the clinician
JTR2		The way in which the algorithm arrived at a certain decision or diagnosis shall be accessible by the clinician
Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness		
JD1	Not ensuring a correct diversity in the group composition from the beginning may end in biases that discriminate one or more groups	A correct and fairly representative group composition shall be achieved by all clinical partners, with inclusion and exclusion criteria defined based on sound scientific principles and respecting the KPIs stated in the DOA
JD2		The used data sets shall be tested and documented at each step (planning, training, testing and deployment)
JD3		Strictly avoid any discrimination in group composition both between patients and between researchers based on sex, gender, race, religion, ethnicity, ensuring that a correct sex and gender as well as ethnicity balance is achieved
JD4		Strictly avoid any discrimination in group composition both between patients and between researchers based on sex, gender, race, religion, ethnicity, ensuring that a correct sex and gender as well as ethnicity balance is achieved
Environmental and societal well being		

Req #ID	Identified Risk	MES-CoBraD Criterium
JE1	The absence of societal concerns and possible impacts on the environment can lead to unwanted discriminations or non-reversible damages to nature resources	The system must incorporate safeguards to prevent systematic discrimination against any social groups employing fairness-aware algorithms

5.1.5 CARE

Table 17 - Care assessment criteria

Req #ID	Identified Risk	MES-CoBraD Criterium
Human agency and oversight		
CH1	External factors, other than the true patients' needs, guide the development of the system. This results into a system that does not meet patients' needs and that might also conflict with them	Consider, during the design phase, the patients' needs, listening to them in dedicated focus groups and co-creation workshops, to design a system that has patients' vision and needs embedded into it from the beginning
CH2		Adequate attention must be given to involving different stakeholders, listening to their viewpoints, and incorporating their feedback into the design and development of the algorithm to ensure that the system meets the needs and preferences of all stakeholders.
CH3		The human assessor evaluating the algorithm must assess its impact on the care relationship, considering not only its performance metrics but also its broader effects on the therapeutic process, patient-provider relationship, and overall patient experience.
CH4		The project research is guided by patients' needs and not by other – external – issues, such as scientific curiosity, advancement of a certain field of research, etc.
CH5		In cases where AI facilitates early diagnosis, the human clinician must strike a balance between the potential risks and benefits of communicating such diagnoses to patients, considering nuanced, non-deterministic factors beyond algorithmic considerations to guide decision-making.
CH6		Before and after the release, user acceptance tests that also involve patients shall be executed
CH7		The patients shall have a way to report their feedback, which shall be taken into consideration by researchers in dedicated and periodical review sessions
Technical robustness and safety		
CT1	Safety and robustness of the system are not taken as a fundamental part of the caring for humans involved	The system must take into account contextual factors when generating algorithmic conclusions (such as environmental conditions, social determinants, and individual circumstances) to ensure that the algorithm's conclusions are reflective of the specific context in which they are applied.
Transparency		

Req #ID	Identified Risk	MES-CoBraD Criterium
CTR1	Only technological parameters (e.g. system robustness) are considered during the design and development phase, bringing to neglect fundamental aspects proper of a care relationship	Patients autonomy and empowerment must be granted by providing them the necessary information to understand and actively participate in the therapeutic process, avoiding paternalistic attitudes and ensuring transparency in all interactions with patients.
Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness		
CD1	Patients' feedback and opinions about something (the care plan) that directly concerns them aren't considered, resulting into discrimination practices, unequal treatment and an unfair approach to research	.Respect of human diversities must be integrated, avoiding a uniform view of individuals and incorporating factors such as culture, ethnicity, gender, and socioeconomic status into its decision-making processes.
CD2		The system must reject a biological deterministic attitude, acknowledging and considering the multifaceted nature of human beings, particularly in healthcare and brain disease contexts, where factors such as social determinants, environmental influences, and individual experiences play crucial roles.
Environmental and societal well being		
CE1	Only technological parameters (e.g. system robustness) are considered during the design and development phase, bringing to neglect fundamental aspects proper of a care relationship	.During the data collection phase, insert also variables about how the patients responded emotionally and psychologically to therapies. Use these variables to suggest the best therapy for a specific patient (matching his/her profile with those in the knowledge base), taking into account not only biological but also emotional factors and aiming at the maximum possible grade of personalization of care (the best therapy for that particular patient)
CE2		Parameters that assess the quality of care shall be identified and the system shall be assessed against them
CE3		The consequences and impact on human beings (both at the individual level and at the societal level) of the introduction of the MES-CoBraD ES shall be evaluated and assessed beforehand and continuously monitored in the post-release phase

6 PARTICIPATION IN STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES

In the preceding sections a set of risks has been identified and a set of requirements/assessment criteria has accordingly been defined. The process that should be followed to operationalize and fully integrate such requirements in the design and development of an AI system has also been described. The result is what it has been called the “ETHAI model”.

The ETHAI model, if adopted, should grant that an AI system positively reflect and integrate the base ethical values and guidelines that constitute the core of the model. Of course, its adoption and integration inside AI systems development is discretionary and the ETHAI can also be applied in separate modules, as it has been done in the course of the MES-CoBraD project, where it acted only as an ex-post assessment tool.

A clear open path for the further development of the ETHAI model would be to formalize it as a technical specification and standard for the ethics-by-conception design and assessment of artificial intelligence technology.

In the light of pursuing this objective, an analysis of the existing standards on ethics of AI has been carried out, discovering the following relevant initiatives and, as it will be specified more in detail later on, major ethics and legal concerns to be addressed:

Figure 9 - Standardisation Working Groups on AI

- ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 “Artificial Intelligence”, that is the international Joint Technical Committee and its specific subgroup addressing the AI topic;
- CEN/CENELEC JTC21 “Artificial Intelligence”, that is the European Joint Technical Committee addressing the AI topic;
- UNI CT 533 “Intelligenza Artificiale”, that is the Italian National body and its specific Technical Committee addressing the AI topic.

Figure 10 - Standardisation Working Groups on AI

Specifically, the CEN and CENELEC have established the new CEN-CENELEC Joint Technical Committee 21 ‘Artificial Intelligence’, based on the recommendations presented in the CEN-CENELEC response to the EC White Paper on AI¹⁰ and therefore to “ensure the development of trustworthy AI systems that respect fundamental values and human rights recognized in Europe”¹¹.

Considering this relevant JTC21 of CEN-CENELEC, in December 2022, CEL contacted the EU contact point (Laurens HERNALSTEEN) and he suggested to participate in and contribute through the Italian branch UNI CT 533. Following the memberships procedure, CEL submitted its request for joining the specific Italian Technical Committee and from March 2023 CEL is member of UNI CT 533.

6.1 ETHICS ASPECTS IN THE FORTHCOMING AI STANDARDS

CEL started its participation in UNI CT 533 meetings and since the beginning emerged a gap between the standardisation activities and results from EC research activities and EU principles:

¹⁰https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/Areas%20of%20Work/Position%20Paper/cen-clc_ai_fg_white-paper-response_final-version_june-2020.pdf

¹¹ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/areas-of-work/cen-cenelec-topics/artificial-intelligence/>

- EU Ethics guidelines for Trustworthy AI were never referenced;
- Fundamental rights (e.g., privacy) were partially covered and considered;
- Forthcoming AI Act and other relevant regulations (e.g., GDPR) were partially considered;
- Lack of awareness on R&I projects and their outcomes in the context of Artificial Intelligence and its use cases.

Given this premise, CEL presented its involvement and results achieved in the MES-CoBraD project and remarked these major concerns. For this reason, UNI CT 533 requested CEL to submit comments to the working-draft ISO/IEC TS 6254:2023(E) “Information technology – Artificial intelligence – Objectives and approaches for explainability of ML models and AI systems”.

The introduction of this document was commented as follow:

<p>Comment 1</p>	<p>“When AI systems are used to help make decisions that impact people’s lives, it is important that people understand how those decisions are made.”</p> <p>I would suggest that “it is important” is not appropriate.</p> <p>In principle, it is a fundamental right to be informed (e.g. GDPR regulation and other ethics principles) about benefits and risks as well.</p>
<p>Proposed Changes 1</p>	<p>When AI systems are used to help make decisions that impact people’s lives (e.g. healthcare), it is a fundamental right for human beings protected by regulations (e.g. General Data Protection Regulation [GDPR] and Medical Device Regulation [MDR]) and ethics principles (e.g. EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI [ETAI]) to understand how those decisions are made, as well as to ensure that the introduction of AI into the decision making process continues to deliver ethically compliant outputs [MO23].</p> <p><i>HERE below additional updated references, not mentioned in the current version:</i></p> <p>[GDPR] Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj</p> <p>[MDR] European Parliament and Council, “Medical Device Regulation 17/745,” 2017. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/746/oj</p> <p>[MO23] Morpurgo, F., Occhipinti, C. Let the AI assisted medicine remain human - Developing a care centered model of ethical decision making in AI based healthcare, in Ital-IA 2023: 3rd National Conference on Artificial Intelligence, https://www.ital-ia2023.it/submission/21/paper organized by CINI, May 29-31, 2023, Pisa, Italy</p>
<p>Comment 2</p>	<p>“For one, this is because whether an AI system is considered explainable depends on the systems, stakeholders, and applications being considered.”</p> <p>Explainability mainly depends on data and business model as well, considering the EU Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI [EUEAI], therefore I kindly suggest to change as suggested.</p> <p>For the sake of clarity, this is how EUEAI defines explainability</p> <p>Explainability concerns the ability to explain both the technical processes of an AI system and the related human decisions (e.g. application areas of a system). Technical explainability requires that the decisions made by an AI system can be understood and traced by human beings. Moreover, trade-offs might have to be made between enhancing a system’s explainability (which may reduce its accuracy) or increasing its accuracy (at the cost of explainability). Whenever an AI system has a significant impact on people’s lives, it should be possible to demand a suitable explanation of the AI system’s decision-making process. Such explanation should be timely and adapted to the expertise of the stakeholder concerned (e.g. layperson, regulator or researcher). In addition, explanations of the degree to which an AI system influences and shapes the organisational decision-making process, design choices of the system, and the rationale for deploying it, should be available (hence ensuring business model transparency).</p>
<p>Proposed Changes 2</p>	<p>“For one, this is because whether an AI system is considered explainable depends on the systems, stak“For one, this is because whether an AI system is considered explainable depends</p>

	on the data [EUEAI], systems, stakeholders, and applications being considered.” <i>HERE below additional updated references, not mentioned in the current version:</i> [EUEAI] European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI, Publications Office, 2019, https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/346720
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Comments were accepted and for this reason, CEL was invited to participate in JTC21/WG3 “Artificial Intelligence – Engineering aspects”.

Since June 2023 CEL is actively contributing to the Working Draft Technical Report (TR) “Data governance and quality for AI within the European context”.

6.2 THE ETHAI MODEL IN JTC21/WG3

The TR provides an overview of the relevant ethics principles and regulations in the European context and connected international standards, paying particular attention to data governance and data quality topics applied to Artificial Intelligence.

This TR was considered the appropriate working document where reporting the ETHAI experience in MES-CoBraD. The TR, that is still a Working Draft (WD), is structured in 12 chapters as follow:

- 1) Scope
- 2) Normative references
- 3) Terms and definitions
- 4) Abbreviations
- 5) JRC Research and Data-related standards on AI
- 6) Data Governance
- 7) Data Quality
- 8) Elements for data, datasets, information for testing and evaluation
- 9) Data Governance and data quality for large European contexts
- 10) General considerations on innovative technology: Ethics, Governance, AI Act
- 11) Potential challenges
- 12) Best practices from organizations, industries and research activities

Specifically, CEL contributed to the last 3 chapters reporting:

- ethics and regulatory principles applied to AI, considering the EU Ethics Guidelines and forthcoming AI Act;
- identified concerns and challenges
- experiences of the MES-CoBraD project and the ETHAI model to mitigate/address the identified concerns. MES-CoBraD is reported as a best practice.

1797 **12 Best practices from organizations, industries and research activities**
 1798 **12.1 General**
 1799 This section aims at presenting few case studies and best practices from industry and research activities,
 1800 specifically attempting to identify and manage challenges when AI-based systems are applied in the
 1801 context of healthcare and critical infrastructures.

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1802 **12.2 AI in Healthcare: the MES-CoBraD approach**
 1803 Pioneering technologies and methodologies have facilitated the advancement of various sectors,
 1804 contributing to the enhanced well-being of our society. This progress has resulted in reduced timelines
 1805 for the production and dissemination of solutions to the public, thereby improving overall quality of life.
 1806 Healthcare services have played a pivotal role in this transformative journey, achieving remarkable

Figure 11 - Extract of the TR

In Feb 2024 the TR was accepted and presented for ballot at European level. A LinkedIn post¹² announced this relevant milestone (Feb 9 2024).

6.3 NEXT STEPS

During the finalisation of this document, the TR is registered as document N 307 (18 March 2024) and is published in the ISO portal for ballot.

CEN/CLC/JTC 21/WG 3 N 307

CEN/CLC/JTC 21/WG 3 "Engineering aspects"
 WG Secretariat: DS
 Convenor: Davenport James Prof

N307 CEN-CLC-JTC 21-WG 3 Data Gov. vers 2.2.3 - 27 February 2024

Document type	Related content	Document date	Expected action
Project / Draft	Project: JT021007 - prCEN/CLC/TR XXX	2024-03-18	

Replaces: N 305 CEN-CLC-JTC 21-WG 3 Data Gov. vers 2.2.3 - 27 February 2024, N 299 CEN-CLC-JTC 21-WG 3 Data Gov. vers 2.2.3 - 27 February 2024

Figure 12 - TR in the ISO portal for ballot

The TR will be kept for ballot along the next three months. Therefore it is expected to deliver a new revision

¹² <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7161651095587565568>

after the ballot (June 2024). It will be also evaluated the integration of (part of) this TR into a working document of the ISO/IEC standardisation.

7 CONCLUSION

Healthcare is one of the main areas of application of artificial intelligence, something probably due to two characterizing factors: the need, in its field of application, of using and interpreting an enormous amount of data and variables, and the extreme complexity of the matter, with an evident **tension between the impulse towards standardisation and the need for personalisation**. The fact that more and more people have access to healthcare, the ageing population, and the growth of knowledge in all fields of the medicine, is causing **an increasing pressure on healthcare providers and a maybe irreversible difficulty in transferring the expert knowledge to enough doctors**. In this panorama **artificial intelligence** may represent an unprecedented opportunity to overcome many of the drawbacks of the current national healthcare systems and to **make knowledge progress at a speed never seen before**.

At the same time, as it is widely known, **artificial intelligence** may be a **gigantic source of ethical and legal problems**, due to its nature and the nature of the data it processes and of the field where it operates. In the course of the present deliverable, but also of the deliverables D2.3 and D2.5 many ethically problematic issues have been thoroughly analysed and discussed. Here, **a model (the ETHAI model) based on a set of ethical values has been defined, for the ethical design and assessment of an artificial intelligence based Expert System, impacting all the phases of the design, development, and use of such a system**.

After having analysed the current debate on bioethics and on which moral theory should lie at the basis of its most renown principles (“beneficence”, “non-maleficence”, “justice”, “autonomy”), the analysis shift on the examination of a particular moral theory, the “ethics of care”, that seem to possess particularly desirable characteristics to lie at the basis of a model for the ethical assessment of an artificial intelligence model as applied to healthcare.

In fact, as it is amply shown during the deliverable, and in particular in section 2.2.4, ethics of care is not properly in conflict with principlism, because principles are fundamentally value agnostic and so ethics of care can act as the moral “soul” of an otherwise pliable shell.

Later on, taking as a reference and adopting as principles the EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, a set of risks is defined, and for each one the applicability to the project and the likelihood of it to happen during the project itself are assessed.

Based on the detected risks a set of ethical assessment criteria is defined, that act as a basis both for the system design and development. Such an approach is shared by many AI assessment frameworks, that are examined and discussed in section 3.1. The ETHAI model inscribes in such a framework, and in the context of the models, such as Edb-AI, that are powered by an ethics by design approach.

The peculiarity of the ETHAI consists of incorporating - and even more - putting at its very core a different value system, to adapt it to its context of application, namely healthcare. It is argued that especially when designing and assessing an AI system that has as its ultimate objective that of performing diagnoses and proposing treatments, as well as evaluating the treatments being administered, an approach that starts from a different perspective – namely that of having as a guiding light primarily the relational nature of human beings and their being both unique and situated in a precise context – could really make the difference and it is well worth exploring.

The articulation of the ETHAI model and the requirements that represent its “engine” are presented in section 3.

The application of the model to a certain AI system (the MES-CoBraD one but also others) will result in an assessment of its ethicality and in a series of point of attention to be examined to improve the feeblest aspects. It’s easy to see how adhering to this process and running this model is important for organizations working with AI, especially in sensible fields. For this reason, CEL engaged in standardisation activities in the context of CEN/CENELEG Joint Technical Committee 21 ‘Artificial

Intelligence’, to transfer the experience gained while developing the ETHAI part of the ongoing “Information technology – Artificial intelligence – Objectives and approaches for explainability of ML models and AI systems”.

The ETHAI model is a work in progress activity. Fields of improvement are twofold: from one hand, it would be necessary to furtherly specify the assessment criteria/requirements, splitting each one of them in smaller bits, capable of being embedded into code; on the other hand, the incorporation of the ethics of care approach is still not complete, and a fully integration of this approach into the developed assessment model still requires work and analysis, maybe in combination with the field of narrative medicine and of neuroethics.

An important aspect that has not been fronted in the current deliverable regards how the model could help not only designers and developers to build the system, but also users (in this case clinicians) to use the system so that the decisions reached with its support are fully ethically based. This is an aspect that will be analysed and discussed in deliverable 2.10 (CoBraD ethical and legal helpdesk report), where the interaction of the users with the system will be considered.

The ETHAI as an assessment model will instead be used in the deliverable D2.8, the final PUCs assessment, to evaluate from the ethical and legal point of view the work done in the context of the PUC #3 and #4, that more strictly concern the MES-CoBraD Expert System.

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